

**VOLUNTARY TURNOVER OF PERSONNEL
IN THE PHILIPPINE MARINE CORPS:
UNDERSTANDING THE FACTORS INFLUENCING ENLISTED PERSONNEL
OF PMC TO VOLUNTARILY LEAVE THE MILITARY SERVICE.**

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**The Governance Innovation Report attached hereto, entitled “VOLUNTARY
TURNOVER OF PERSONNEL IN THE PHILIPPINE MARINE CORPS:
UNDERSTANDING THE FACTORS INFLUENCING ENLISTED PERSONNEL
OF PMC TO VOLUNTARILY LEAVE THE MILITARY SERVICE” prepared and
submitted by NELSON P. LIWANAG in partial fulfilment of the requirements for
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LIST of ACRONYMS

AFP - Armed Forces of the Philippines

CDR - Coastal Defense Regiment

CMB - Career Management Branch

EP - Enlisted Personnel

MCIB - Marine Corps Intelligence Battalion

MC1 - Assistant Chief of Marine Corps Staff for Personnel

SNCO - Senior NCO

MOND - Ministry of National Defense

NSP - National Security Policy

NSS - National Security Strategy

NDS - National Defense Strategy

PMC - Philippine Marine Corps

SCS - South China Sea

SET - Social Exchange Theory

WPS - West Philippine Sea

ABSTRACT

Voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps presents a significant challenge to operational readiness, unit cohesion, and organizational stability. This study examines the factors influencing voluntary turnover and proposes strategies to enhance personnel retention. Personal, professional, and organizational factors including job-related stress, job mismatch, leadership support, career satisfaction, and work-life balance are analyzed to determine their impact on personnel attrition. An explanatory sequential design approach, combining surveys, interviews, and document analysis, was employed to collect data from enlisted personnel across various PMC units nationwide. Quantitative findings identify patterns in turnover intentions, while qualitative data provide deeper insights into individual motivations for leaving the service. Results indicate that leadership support, administrative policies, and workplace culture significantly influence retention, with job dissatisfaction and family responsibilities emerging as primary drivers of voluntary separation. The study highlights the necessity of a comprehensive retention program that addresses financial incentives, career development, leadership engagement, and family support mechanisms. Enhancing these aspects is essential to reducing voluntary turnover and ensuring the PMC maintains a highly skilled and committed force capable of fulfilling its mission requirements. This research contributes to the development of evidence-based policies to improve personnel retention within the PMC.

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The Philippine Marine Corps (PMC), established in 1950, is a critical component of the Armed Forces of the Philippines, specializing in amphibious operations and coastal defense. Over the years, it has evolved to address various security challenges, including territorial defense, counter-insurgency, and disaster response. This evolution, while enhancing the PMC's operational capabilities, has introduced significant demands on its personnel.

A persistent challenge faced by military organizations is not only the recruitment of personnel but also the lack of effective retention programs. Manpower constitutes a fundamental military resource, and when endowed with the appropriate qualities and competencies, it ensures the successful execution of mission-essential tasks. It is through motivated and proficient individuals that military investments in weapon systems and equipment can be transformed into effective military capabilities, which are crucial for addressing diverse security scenarios. Following recruitment and training, the organization's responsibility extends to equipping, maintaining, and optimizing manpower and equipment

to develop a dependable military capability. With this, the retention of personnel emerges as a critical component in sustaining a credible defense force.

Since its inception, the PMC has grappled with significant voluntary turnover among its enlisted personnel. Despite initiatives aimed at enhancing retention, persistent turnover has adversely affected operational readiness and organizational stability, as evidenced by ongoing challenges in maintaining a committed and experienced workforce. This problem has negatively impacted PMC personnel, their families, and overall operational effectiveness. Enlisted personnel, facing high levels of job-related stress and struggling to balance military duties with personal life, often cite these factors as reasons for leaving the service voluntarily.

The issue of voluntary turnover among personnel is a growing concern for the Philippine Marine Corps. This turnover rates of EP from 2017 to 2023, highlights the need to understand and address the underlying factors contributing to this phenomenon.

On average, the PMC has seen around 300 personnel voluntarily leaving each year over the past six years as reflected in table 1. This rate of turnover not only affects the corps' operational effectiveness but also incurs substantial costs related to recruiting and training new personnel.

Table 1. Records of Voluntary Turnover of PMC personnel from 2017-2023

	CALENDAR YEAR						
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Optional Retirement	7 OFFR/	12 OFFR/	14 OFFR/	14 OFFR/	4 OFFR/	15 OFFR/	16 OFFR/
		239 EP	229 EP	232 EP	161 EP	291 EP	226 EP
Dependency Discharge upon ETE	18 EP	83 EP	115 EP	60 EP	67 EP	60 EP	88 EP
AWOL	89	27 EP	21 EP	7 EP	2 EP	2 EP	13 EP
Total	7 OFFR/ 107 EP	12 OFFR/ 349 EP	14 OFFR/ 365 EP	14 OFFR/ 299 EP	4 OFFR/ 230 EP	15 OFFR/ 353 EP	16 OFFR/ 367 EP

The rapid pace of modernization and the introduction of new technologies further complicate these challenges. Despite these positive developments, there are potential implications for personnel turnover. The rapid pace of modernization and the introduction of new technologies necessitate extensive training and adaptation, which can be demanding and stressful for personnel. This stress may lead to job dissatisfaction among those who struggle to keep up with new requirements or feel overwhelmed by the increased complexity of their roles and the overwhelming skill sets required to operate modern equipment.

A possible cause of voluntary turnover is the mismatch between job expectations and the actual work environment experienced by PMC personnel. Compounding this issue is the lack of comprehensive research exploring the factors driving this turnover, particularly within the context of the PMC. This study aims to address this gap by analyzing the personal-professional and organizational factors contributing to voluntary turnover and proposing innovative solutions to enhance retention strategies.

Statement of the Problem

The Philippine Marine Corps (PMC) has been experiencing a significant and persistent issue with voluntary turnover among its enlisted personnel. This challenge affects the PMC's operational readiness, organizational stability, and ability to fulfill its mission mandates. High rates of turnover, driven by factors such as job-related stress, professional challenges, and organizational demands, disrupt unit cohesion, increase training costs, and diminish overall efficiency. Addressing this problem requires a comprehensive analysis of the factors influencing personnel turnover and the development of effective retention strategies.

To address these issues, this study seeks to analyze the following research questions:

1. What personal and professional factors, including job satisfaction, influence voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps?
2. What organizational factors, such as leadership support and job-related stress, contribute to turnover decisions?
3. What types of programs or interventions can effectively address the identified issues and gaps related to voluntary turnover?

Objectives of the Study

General Objective: To analyze the personal, professional and organizational factors influencing voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps and propose actionable strategies to mitigate this issue.

Specific Research Objectives:

1. To identify the personal and professional factors, including job satisfaction, that influence voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps;
2. To determine the organizational factors, such as leadership support and job-related stress, contribute to turnover decisions; and
3. To examine types of programs or interventions that can effectively address the identified issues and gaps related to voluntary turnover.

Innovation Objective: To design and propose a comprehensive retention program for the Philippine Marine Corps that addresses both personal-professional and organizational factors contributing to voluntary turnover. The goal is to develop targeted interventions addressing the identified personal, professional, and organizational factors contributing to turnover and propose evidence-based strategies and programs to reduce voluntary turnover in the Philippine Marine Corps.

Significance of the Study

This study contributed new insights into the factors influencing voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps (PMC). As the first comprehensive study of its kind within the institution, it filled a significant knowledge gap and provided a foundation for future research and strategic planning aimed at improving retention rates.

The findings of this study can directly inform the development of targeted retention programs within the PMC. By understanding the specific factors driving turnover, PMC leadership can tailor interventions to enhance job satisfaction, address job mismatch, and support personnel in managing family responsibilities and work-life balance. This can lead to more effective program implementation and operational outcomes, ultimately strengthening the PMC's readiness and operational effectiveness.

The research outcomes has the potential to influence policies within the PMC by advocating for evidence-based strategies to mitigate voluntary turnover. Specific policies may include revisions to recruitment practices, enhancements in training and development programs, and the establishment of support mechanisms to address personnel concerns identified in the study. Additionally, the study may contribute to broader military policy discussions regarding retention strategies and workforce management.

Table 2. Potential Stakeholder benefits from the Study

Research End User	Potential Benefits from the Study
Philippine Marine Corps Leadership	Gain insights into specific factors contributing to voluntary turnover, enabling targeted interventions to improve retention and operational readiness.
PMC Personnel	Understand the organizational dynamics affecting retention decisions, leading to improved job satisfaction, support mechanisms, and work-life balance initiatives.
Military Policy Makers	Utilize research findings to shape national defense policies related to personnel management, enhancing overall military readiness and effectiveness.
Academic Researchers	Access a comprehensive dataset and methodology for future studies on military personnel retention and organizational behavior within the context of national security.

Research End User	Potential Benefits from the Study
Government Officials	Use evidence-based recommendations from the study to support legislative efforts aimed at improving military personnel welfare and retention in the national security framework.

Scope Limitation and Delimitation of the Study

Scope

The study focuses on investigating the factors influencing voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps (PMC). It examines personal, professional, and organizational factors within PMC bases and operational environments in the Philippines for CY 2025. Key factors examined include personal factors such as family responsibilities and work life balance. It includes also job-related stress, job satisfaction, job mismatch, and organizational perceptions and actions related to turnover within the PMC. Factors such as broader national economic conditions, global geopolitical influences, and external military policies beyond the control of the PMC are excluded from the study's scope.

Limitations

Limitations that include potential biases in self-reported data from surveys and interviews, as well as constraints in accessing personnel records and historical data due to privacy regulations are to be considered. Practical constraints such as time limitations for data collection and resource constraints for extensive fieldwork are also acknowledged.

Delimitations

The study is focused solely on internal dynamics and organizational responses within the PMC, excluding broader external factors that may indirectly impact turnover rates.

Definition of Terms

Amphibious Warfare - Military operations launched from the sea by naval and amphibious forces to achieve objectives on land.

Counter-Insurgency Operations - Military actions aimed at combating and defeating insurgent groups within a country.

Coastal Defense Regiment (CDR) - A unit within the PMC focused on defending the country's coastlines against external threats with shore based missiles capability.

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory - A theory that divides job factors into motivators (which enhance job satisfaction) and hygiene factors (which prevent dissatisfaction).

Job Embeddedness Theory - A framework that explains how employees' connections, alignment with organizational values, and perceived costs of leaving affect their decision to stay or leave.

Job Mismatch - A situation where there is a discrepancy between an individual's job expectations and the actual work experience.

Job-Related Stress - Stress experienced by employees due to their job demands and work environment.

Job Satisfaction: The level of contentment employees feel about their job roles and responsibilities.

Key Budgetary Unit (KBU) - A status that allows more efficient allocation and utilization of resources within an organization. An organizational entity within the military that has its own financial management and autonomy, allowing it to allocate and use funds independently from the central command.

Marine Corps Intelligence Battalion (MCIB) - A specialized unit responsible for gathering and analyzing intelligence to support PMC operations.

Normative Psychological Pressure - The psychological force that influences individuals to adhere to social norms and expectations.

Operational Effectiveness - The ability of an organization to achieve its goals and objectives effectively.

Retention Programs - Initiatives designed to keep employees from leaving an organization and improve job satisfaction.

Social Exchange Theory (SET) - A theory that posits individuals weigh the costs and benefits of their interactions and relationships, influencing their commitment and turnover decisions.

Voluntary Turnover - refers to the intentional and self-initiated departure of employees from an organization. This type of turnover occurs when personnel choose to leave their positions for reasons that are within their control, such as seeking new job opportunities, pursuing career advancements, relocating, or leaving the workforce altogether.

Voluntary Turnover Rates - The frequency at which employees voluntarily leave an organization, which can differ based on various factors including organizational culture and external conditions.

Work-Life Balance - The equilibrium between personal life and professional responsibilities

Review of Literature

Historical Context and Evolution of the Philippine Marine Corps

The Philippine Marine Corps (PMC), an integral part of the Armed Forces of the Philippines (AFP), was established on November 7, 1950, as the 1st Marine Company under the Philippine Naval Patrol. This creation was in response to the strategic necessity for a specialized amphibious force capable of operating across the archipelagic terrain of the Philippines. Over the decades, the PMC has continually evolved, expanding its capabilities to address the nation's dynamic security challenges (Camagay, 2020).

The creation of the PMC was a strategic initiative during President Ramon Magsaysay's term, inspired by the U.S. Marine Corps. In its early years, the PMC focused on amphibious warfare training and operations. Rigorous training programs, often patterned with the United States Marine Corps, were a hallmark of this period, enhancing the PMC's operational capabilities and fostering a strong professional relationship with its US counterpart. These foundational efforts were critical in shaping the PMC's operational doctrines and preparedness (Camagay, 2020).

The 1970s and 1980s marked a significant era for the PMC with numerous counter-insurgency operations against various armed groups within the Philippines. These operations underscored the versatility and resilience of the PMC across diverse environments, from dense jungles to urban landscapes. During this period, the organizational structure of the

PMC expanded, with additional battalions and specialized units being formed to enhance operational effectiveness (Camagay, 2020).

In recent years, the PMC has modernized and adapted to contemporary security threats, participating in joint and combined operations with international partners, focusing on counter-terrorism, humanitarian assistance, and disaster response. The PMC's role in international peacekeeping missions further underscores its commitment to global security and stability.

The historical evolution of the PMC has significant implications for current challenges, particularly voluntary turnover. As the PMC has grown and its operational scope has widened, the pressures and demands on personnel have also increased. Historical changes have directly impacted personnel policies and retention strategies over the years.

Recent Developments and Current Operations

In recent years, the PMC has evolved into an Archipelagic Coastal Defense Force. Significant milestones include the activation of the Coastal Defense Regiment (CDR) and the Marine Corps Intelligence Battalion (MCIB) to enhance coastal defense capabilities. The Philippines has also become the first foreign nation to acquire the Indian-Russian BrahMos supersonic anti-ship missile, with a \$374 million contract awarded to BrahMos Aerospace Pvt Ltd to enhance its naval defenses (Strangio, 2022).

The PMC has also achieved Key Budgetary Unit (KBU) status, enabling more efficient resource utilization. This status enabled the PMC to establish additional units and offices, such as the Coastal defense Regiment, Service Support Regiment, PMC Supply

Center and Finance Center (PMC, 2019). While these developments signify modernization, they also underscore the increasing demands on personnel, heightening the risk of voluntary turnover.

Understanding these advancements invites an exploration of global trends in military turnover, which share both parallels and contrasts with the Philippine context.

Global Perspective on Voluntary Turnover

Research identifies several critical factors influencing voluntary turnover. Studies indicate that job satisfaction, normative psychological pressure, organizational commitment, career opportunities, leadership quality, and work-life balance significantly impact turnover intentions (Maertz & Campion, 1998; Huang, Lawler, & Lei, 2007). Marc Holliday (2021) highlighted that lack of competitive compensation, being overworked, poor work/life balance and negative culture are the common reasons for voluntary turnover of personnel. In global contexts, turnover rates vary due to differences in military culture, economic conditions, and geopolitical factors. These factors resonate across different armed forces, underscoring universal challenges in retention. Furthermore, Norris (2004) emphasized the importance of understanding the specific reasons behind employee departures, as voluntary turnover can lead to the loss of critical experience and expertise, negatively impacting operations. The study conducted by Norris (2004) aimed to assess the relationships between role stressors, job satisfaction, and turnover intentions, providing valuable insights into the multifaceted nature of turnover in the military context.

Gebremichael (2019) discussed various factors within the work environment, such as the characteristics of the organization, behavior of supervisors, and the state of the economy, play a crucial role in influencing employee turnover. Employees often leave due to dissatisfaction with their current job or organization, seeking better opportunities and improved living standards elsewhere. Additionally, aspects such as job satisfaction, management style, availability of employment opportunities, and individual personality traits are significant determinants in the decision to stay or leave an organization.

While global trends provide valuable insights, each military organization operates within a distinct cultural and socio-political framework. This necessitates a closer examination of international military turnover strategies to identify potential lessons for the PMC.

International Contexts

Military turnover rates vary significantly across nations due to differences in organizational structures, recruitment policies, and socio-political climates. In the United States Armed Forces, voluntary turnover is influenced by a range of factors, with withdrawal intentions and job withdrawal serving as significant predictors. Withdrawal intention refers to the cognitive process where service members contemplate leaving the military, while job withdrawal involves behaviors indicating disengagement from their roles, such as increased absenteeism (Lytell & Drasgow, 2009). The role of military tenure is also notable; longer service durations often correlate with a lower likelihood of turnover, as the accumulation of experience and benefits can enhance retention.

Organizational commitment is another key factor, encompassing the emotional attachment and loyalty of service members towards the military. Lower levels of organizational commitment are linked to higher turnover intentions (Lytell & Drasgow, 2009). Additionally, background variables, including personal circumstances and demographic characteristics, play a role in turnover decisions. Military satisfaction, reflecting the contentment with job roles and conditions, is crucial; higher satisfaction generally correlates with lower voluntary turnover (Lytell & Drasgow, 2009). The comparison of military versus civilian work environments also affects turnover. Service members often evaluate the relative benefits and drawbacks of their military careers against civilian job opportunities and lifestyle conditions. Economic conditions, job availability, and perceived work-life balance in civilian roles can influence these decisions (Lytell & Drasgow, 2009)

In Europe, retaining military personnel has become a critical issue, exacerbated by rising security threats and competitive job markets. In France, retention is declining, prompting increased retirement pensions and salary boosts as part of a broader strategy to improve retention (Kayali & Posaner, 2024). Germany faces similar challenges, with a significant number of soldiers leaving the Bundeswehr and discussions about potentially reinstating conscription or expanding national service to address personnel shortages (Kayali & Posaner, 2024). Poland has responded with substantial pay increases to retain troops amid growing security concerns (Kayali & Posaner, 2024).

In the United Kingdom, military personnel leave the armed forces for various reasons, significantly impacting their transition to civilian life. Factors influencing this

decision include dissatisfaction with the work environment, perceived lack of career advancement, and financial concerns. Service members often find that the challenges of frequent relocations and the rigidity of military life become less appealing as they grow older and seek better work-life balance or wish to spend more time with family (Roth, 2018). Financial incentives, such as improved pension plans and voluntary severance schemes, play a crucial role in their decision-making process. Additionally, many service members experience frustration with outdated technology and inadequate living conditions, which can further motivate their departure from the military (Roth, 2018).

Building on the international context, it is essential to explore how turnover challenges manifest within the Philippine Navy, particularly in relation to the PMC's unique operational demands.

Philippine Navy's Context

In the context of the Philippine Navy personnel retention challenges are marked by discrepancies in personnel reports, insufficient career development, and low morale, leading to high turnover rates as articulated in PN Human Capital Strategy. Issues include a misalignment between assigned roles and actual skills, unfilled senior positions, and outdated career management systems. The PN's strategic response emphasizes improving human resource management through selective recruitment, sound career management, and an innovative retention program. This includes addressing administrative inefficiencies, enhancing training and career development opportunities, and improving personnel morale with better housing and life skills training to retain a highly competent workforce amidst modernization efforts and external threats (PN Human Capital Strategy, 2013).

Synthesis

The literature review reveals that voluntary turnover among military personnel is influenced by a complex interplay of global, and contextual factors and grounded in established models and theories that explain employee turnover. Global perspectives highlight job satisfaction, career opportunities, and work environment as pivotal factors affecting turnover. The Unfolding Model of Voluntary Turnover by Lee and Mitchell (1994) provides the foundation for understanding the dynamic interplay between external shocks, organizational factors, and personal circumstances that influence decisions to leave.

The study further utilizes established frameworks, such as Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory and Social Exchange Theory that offer valuable insights into the motivation and retention of personnel, emphasizing the importance of addressing both satisfaction and dissatisfaction. Methodological approaches, including mixed-methods studies, provide comprehensive insights into turnover predictors and personal experiences. International contexts further illustrate how different countries address turnover, with various strategies to improve retention. Just like any organization, the Philippine Navy faces unique challenges, including career development issues and low morale. These insights highlights the need for a tailored approach to address the specific factors influencing voluntary turnover in the Philippine Marine Corps.

Research Limitations

Despite these insights, significant gaps remain in understanding the factors influencing voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps (PMC). Current research often neglects the personal and professional factors specific to this unique military environment, which are critical for analyzing the dynamics of turnover. While general studies address job-related stress and job satisfaction, limited exploration exists on how these factors, along with job mismatch, specifically affect the decision of PMC personnel to leave the service voluntarily.

Additionally, organizational factors influencing voluntary turnover in the PMC remain underexplored. A detailed investigation into how organizational practices, policies, and perceptions contribute to turnover is crucial for understanding and addressing these challenges.

Furthermore, the role of family responsibilities and work-life balance in shaping retention within the PMC context has received insufficient attention. These personal factors are particularly relevant in the highly demanding operational environment of the PMC and require a more focused analysis.

Finally, while traditional retention strategies are well-documented, there is a pressing need for innovative retention programs tailored to the specific challenges of PMC personnel.

These programs must address personal factors, organizational issues, and psychological stressors, including work-life balance and job mismatch, to enhance overall retention.

This study does not aim to resolve the issue of voluntary turnover directly but seeks to contribute to the body of knowledge by addressing the challenges faced by the PMC related to Voluntary turnover of personnel. Analyzing the specific personal, professional, and organizational factors influencing turnover within the Philippine Marine Corps (PMC) through this paper could valuable insights that can inform future retention strategies and interventions.

Applicable Theoretical Frameworks for Understanding Retention and Turnover

Theoretical frameworks on employee motivation, such as Herzberg's two-factor theory, provide valuable insights into understanding military turnover. Herzberg's theory differentiates between motivation factors, which contribute to job satisfaction, and hygiene factors, which prevent dissatisfaction (Peramatzis & Galanakis, 2022). In the context of the PMC, Motivators, such as recognition and awards, career advancement, and a sense of achievement, contribute to job satisfaction and drive the enlisted personnel to perform at their best. Conversely, hygiene factors, such as salary, working conditions, and job security, do not enhance satisfaction but can cause dissatisfaction when inadequate. An insufficient compensation or poor working conditions can lead to dissatisfaction, prompting enlisted personnel to leave. Motivators, when absent, fail to encourage personnel to stay, further exacerbating turnover rates. This distinction is crucial in the military context, where satisfaction and dissatisfaction arise from different aspects of the job. In the Philippine Marine Corps, addressing motivation factors like responsibility and career growth, alongside

hygiene factors such as working conditions and compensation, can help mitigate voluntary turnover. Understanding how these factors interact within the PMC's operational environment is essential to designing effective retention strategies.

Social Exchange Theory (SET) provides a useful lens for examining the factors influencing voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps. SET posits that individuals weigh the costs and benefits of their relationships and interactions within organizations (Ahmad, Nawaz, Ishaq, Khan, & Ashraf, 2023). If personnel perceive an imbalance in the reciprocity of their exchanges—whether they feel undervalued or unfairly treated—they may be more likely to disengage and leave the service. This theory highlights the importance of fair treatment, recognition, and supportive interactions in maintaining personnel commitment and reducing turnover. Incorporating SET into the analysis of turnover helps identify how perceived inequities and the quality of social exchanges within the Marine Corps could contribute to voluntary exits.

Another relevant and appropriate framework for the study is the Exit-Voice-Loyalty-Neglect (EVLN) Model, which provides a comprehensive lens for analyzing how individuals respond to dissatisfaction within organizations and can be directly applied to understanding voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps.

The Exit-Voice-Loyalty-Neglect (EVLN) Model, originally developed by Hirschman (1970) and later refined by organizational behavior scholars, explains how individuals respond to dissatisfaction within organizations through four key behaviors. These key behaviors include exit (leaving the organization), voice (expressing dissatisfaction in hopes of improvement), loyalty (patiently waiting for conditions to

improve), and neglect (passive withdrawal of effort)(Psychology Fanatic, 2024). . In the context of the PMC, this model offers an insightful framework for understanding how enlisted personnel cope with job dissatisfaction. Voluntary turnover represented by the “exit” response in the model, can be seen as a rational outcome when Marines perceive limited opportunities to express concerns, see no signs of change, or feel their loyalty is unrewarded. This model is also relevant in the study to gain a clearer lens to interpret behavioral patterns leading to voluntary resignation and identify organizational gaps in addressing grievances or providing career fulfillment. Thus, the EVLN model is a fitting theoretical framework that deepens the understanding of the psychosocial and organizational dynamics influencing a Marine's decision to leave the service.

Another theory that can provide valuable insights into understanding why individuals might choose to stay in their positions even when they face potential dissatisfaction or external opportunities is the Job Embeddedness theory as discussed by Lee, Burch, and Mitchell (2014). This theory is particularly relevant for analyzing the voluntary turnover of enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps.

According to Lee, Burch, and Mitchell (2014), Job Embeddedness encompasses three main dimensions: links, fit, and sacrifice. Links refer to the connections an employee has with other people or activities within their organization and community. Fit describes how well an individual's values, needs, and goals align with their job and community. Sacrifice involves the perceived costs or losses associated with leaving a job, such as giving up benefits, relationships, or status. For enlisted personnel in the PMC, these dimensions can be crucial in understanding their decisions to remain or leave the

service. Links might include strong relationships with fellow Marines and Officers, which can create a sense of belonging and loyalty to the unit. Fit could involve how well the personnel's values align with the core values of the Marine Corps and the overall lifestyle it demands. Sacrifice on the other hand may involve the perceived difficulties in transitioning to civilian life, including the loss of military benefits, job security, and the challenges of adapting to a new career or lifestyle.

Employee turnover is a multifaceted phenomenon that requires a nuanced understanding of the decision-making processes that lead individuals to leave an organization. Lee and Mitchell (1994) proposed the Unfolding Model of voluntary employee turnover, which emphasizes the complex interplay of personal, situational, and organizational factors over time. According to their work, traditional models of employee turnover often oversimplify the process, failing to capture the diverse pathways through which individuals decide to exit an organization. They argue that leaving a job is not a singular, uniform decision but can occur through various mechanisms shaped by distinct factors and circumstances.

A critical concept in their model is the "shock to the system," which refers to a significant event that prompts individuals to reassess their current employment situation. These shocks can be positive, negative, or neutral and may stem from either job-related or non-job-related factors. For instance, receiving an unexpected promotion (positive shock) or experiencing a conflict with a supervisor (negative shock) could lead an employee to deliberate about their future in the organization. Interestingly, in some cases, the decision to leave may not involve extensive cognitive evaluation. Instead, employees may act on pre-

determined responses or "scripts" triggered by these shocks, bypassing a thorough consideration of alternatives.

Moreover, not all employees evaluate alternative employment opportunities before deciding to leave. Lee and Mitchell (1994) highlight that many employees focus solely on the decision to stay or exit their current organization without necessarily transitioning to another job. This decision-making process often revolves around assessing the alignment between the individual's values, needs, and the organizational environment—referred to as the "fit" or compatibility criterion—rather than a calculation of maximizing expected outcomes.

Another significant insight from the Unfolding Model is that turnover is not an instantaneous event but rather a process that unfolds over time. Lee and Mitchell (1994) emphasize the importance of understanding this temporal dimension to better identify and address the underlying reasons for employee departures. They also propose further research into the sequencing and categorization of shocks, as well as methods for empirically testing these dynamics. Despite decades of research, accurately predicting turnover remains a challenge, underscoring the need for innovative theoretical and practical approaches to understanding and mitigating turnover.

This perspective provides valuable insights for both researchers and managers aiming to improve retention strategies. By recognizing the complexity and variability in turnover processes, organizations can better tailor interventions to address the specific factors influencing employees' decisions to leave.

CHAPTER II

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND METHODOLOGY

Theoretical framework

The foundation of this study's theoretical framework is the Unfolding Model of Voluntary Turnover introduced by Lee and Mitchell in 1994. This model views employee turnover as a complex and dynamic process that can follow multiple pathways. Unlike the traditional view, which often reduces turnover to a straightforward reaction to job dissatisfaction, this model highlights the interplay of external events, personal circumstances, and workplace factors in shaping turnover decisions.

Central to the model is the concept of a shock to the system, defined as a significant event that disrupts an employee's cognitive and emotional equilibrium (Lee & Mitchell, 1994, p. 60). This shock prompts an evaluation of their current job and possible alternative opportunities. Lee and Mitchell (1994) argue that shocks can vary widely in nature, encompassing positive, neutral, or negative events, and may arise from both job-related and non-job-related sources. For example, a shock could involve a change in leadership, a new family obligation, or a missed promotion.

The model also proposes that some turnover decisions are the result of immediate, habitual responses to shocks, where employees follow scripted behavior without extensive deliberation. In the Unfolding Model of Voluntary Turnover, "scripted behaviors" refer to pre-determined actions that individuals take in response to specific events or "shocks." For

instance, an enlisted Marine who has decided to resign if a promised promotion is not received follows a scripted behavior when that promotion fails to materialize. Conversely, other decisions evolve gradually as dissatisfaction accumulates over time. In many cases, employees base their decisions on the degree of fit or compatibility between their personal values, career goals, and the organizational environment, rather than focusing solely on maximizing perceived benefits.

According to Lee and Mitchell (1994), employee turnover occurs as a process, and understanding this process requires longitudinal analysis to uncover how decisions to leave unfold over time. The Unfolding Model emphasizes the role of time in turnover decisions and argue that these processes often unfold gradually. It also argues that turnover is not always a result of rational decision-making or the pursuit of better alternatives; some employees leave without exploring other job options, making their decision based purely on their desire to stay or leave their current organization.

In the context of this study, the Unfolding Model provides a comprehensive framework to examine the voluntary turnover of enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps. This approach aligns with the research objectives by addressing the personal, professional and organizational factors influencing turnover, including family responsibilities, job satisfaction, and job mismatch, as well as the organizational factors, such as policies, leadership, and workplace relationships. In the context of the Unfolding Model of Voluntary Turnover, shocks are defined as significant events that disrupt an individual's cognitive and emotional equilibrium, prompting reassessment of their commitment to the organization (Lee & Mitchell, 1994). Examples of personal shocks include family emergencies or major life events such as illness of dependents, while

professional shocks may involve sudden leadership changes, unmet career expectations and career stagnation when unexpected, or job-related stress.

For this study, we consider job-related stress and dissatisfaction as professional shocks when they arise unexpectedly or escalate rapidly due to organizational changes or unforeseen circumstances. For instance, personnel who face abrupt increases in workload or operational demands without adequate support may perceive this as a professional shock influencing their turnover decision.

The insights provided by this theoretical framework enable a nuanced analysis of how PMC personnel perceive their work environment and how these perceptions interact with personal circumstances and external shocks to influence turnover decisions. As Lee and Mitchell (1994) note, turnover research requires innovative theoretical approaches to better predict and understand why individuals choose to leave. This study aims to contribute to this understanding by applying the Unfolding Model in the unique setting of military service, ultimately supporting the development of strategies to enhance retention in the PMC.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework on the Unfolding Model of Voluntary Turnover

The Unfolding Model of Voluntary Turnover by Lee and Mitchell (1994) does not provide an illustrated framework. However, the researcher created a visual representation of the model in the figure above to better capture its principles and how they relate to this study. The figure above is adapted from the concepts presented by Lee and Mitchell, illustrating the complex and dynamic process individuals undergo when deciding whether to leave or remain in an organization.

Central to the model is the idea of a "shock to the system," a critical trigger that prompts employees to reevaluate their employment situation. This shock can manifest in various ways, such as a negative workplace experience, a positive external opportunity, or a neutral life event. It may stem from personal or job-related factors, often initiating the turnover process.

The model emphasizes that employees may respond to shocks in different ways. In some cases, the shock results in scripted behavior, where employees act automatically based on pre-existing plans or expectations. For example, someone who has already decided to leave after a promotion denial may act immediately upon experiencing this shock. In other instances, individuals enter a deliberative process where they carefully evaluate their current role, organizational fit, and possible alternatives. This process often involves a detailed assessment of compatibility with the organization, job satisfaction, and future prospects.

For some employees, the primary decision is not about choosing between their current organization and a specific alternative but rather about whether their present situation aligns with their values and career goals. They may decide to leave simply because the role no longer fits, even if no other opportunity is waiting. Others may be deterred from leaving due to the perceived sacrifices involved, such as losing benefits, stability, or established professional relationships. The perception of these sacrifices can be a significant factor in retaining employees, even in situations where dissatisfaction exists.

The model also highlights that turnover is not an instantaneous event but a process that evolves over time. Employees may revisit their decisions multiple times, influenced by new shocks, changing circumstances, or the outcomes of their deliberations. This iterative nature underscores the need for organizations to understand and address the factors contributing to turnover at every stage.

The diagram captures these elements by presenting shocks as a central trigger, branching into different pathways that represent various decision-making processes. It simplifies the complex interactions while preserving the core ideas of the theory, making the

model accessible and applicable to understanding voluntary turnover in the context of the Philippine Marine Corps.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study, rooted in the Unfolding Model of Voluntary Turnover, focuses on understanding the complex factors influencing enlisted personnel of the Philippine Marine Corps (PMC) to voluntarily leave the service. While the theoretical framework provides a general foundation for examining turnover, this conceptual framework narrows its scope to address the unique challenges faced by PMC personnel, aligning it directly with the study's research objectives.

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Central to this framework is the concept of a "shock to the system," a significant event or series of events that disrupt an individual's emotional and cognitive equilibrium. These shocks, whether personal or organizational, are often the catalysts for a reassessment of one's commitment to the service. In the military, personal shocks may include being away from family for extended periods, the strain of long deployments, or the constant danger associated with the job. Organizational shocks, on the other hand, could stem from leadership changes, career stagnation, unmet expectations such as delayed promotions, or feelings of not being a good fit for the role. These shocks create a tipping point, forcing personnel to reconsider their position and evaluate their future with the PMC.

Responses to shocks in the workplace are varied and influenced by individual priorities, circumstances, and goals. For some enlisted personnel, the response to a shock is immediate and follows a pre-determined plan or expectation. For example, a Marine Sergeant may file optional retirement immediately after failing to receive an anticipated promotion, viewing it as a clear signal to pursue other opportunities. For others, the process is more reflective and deliberate, involving a comprehensive evaluation of their job satisfaction, organizational fit, and alignment with personal and professional goals. This reflective phase often includes weighing alternative opportunities and assessing the trade-offs between remaining in service or transitioning to a different career. Factors such as camaraderie within the unit, positive workplace relationships, and access to benefits can sometimes persuade personnel to stay, even when dissatisfaction exists.

The decision-making process is shaped by a complex interplay of personal, professional, and organizational factors. Personal and professional challenges, such as job mismatch, career-family conflicts, and the difficulty of achieving work-life balance in a demanding environment, significantly influence outcomes. Many Marines face stressors like high operational tempo, prolonged separations from loved ones, and the inherent risks associated with military service. On the organizational side, elements such as leadership quality, unit culture, policies, and interpersonal relationships within the workplace play a critical role. A supportive and cohesive unit, characterized by mutual respect and healthy relationships, can alleviate dissatisfaction and foster a sense of belonging, which may counteract the effects of these shocks. The framework also includes the existence of a retention program which can affect the decision of the personnel to either leave or stay in the service as an effective retention program can absorb the shocks being experienced by the personnel. On the other hand, the absence of an effective and comprehensive retention program will result in the decision of the personnel to leave the service.

The framework above suggests that shocks serve as catalysts for a state of inequilibrium and deliberation stage, where individuals reassess their circumstances and deliberate whether to stay in the service or leave. While it is impossible to predict precisely how any individual will respond to a shock, understanding that these shocks initiate a decision-making process offers valuable insights. This knowledge can help the understanding of the complexity of the interactions of shocks is essential for addressing voluntary turnover effectively. The framework not only explains how these decisions unfold but also guides the development of targeted interventions.

Operational Framework

The operational framework for this study utilizes the Input, Process, Output, and Outcome (IPOO) model to systematically examine the factors influencing voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel of the Philippine Marine Corps (PMC). The IPO model serves as the guiding structure for the research, ensuring that each phase of the study is interconnected and follows a clear pathway from data gathering to actionable recommendations (Canonizado, 2024). This model ensures that each phase of the study is systematically connected, offering a clear pathway from data gathering to actionable recommendations.

Figure 3. Operational Framework of the Study

The input stage of this study focuses on the key elements that form the foundation for understanding voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps. The primary inputs are the personal experiences of Marines who have chosen to leave, the organizational factors that influence their decisions, and the retention programs designed to keep them in service.

The personal experiences of Marines who have decided to leave the service are crucial in understanding voluntary turnover. These experiences involve the emotional and psychological challenges faced during their time in the military, including the pressures of deployments, issues with work-life balance, and the personal sacrifices required for a career in the armed forces. Such factors can contribute to feelings of dissatisfaction or misalignment with personal goals, leading to the decision to leave.

Organizational factors also play a significant role in shaping a Marine's decision to leave. These may include negative interactions with leadership, changes in the unit's culture, strained relationships with fellow Marines, or perceived unfairness within the organization. This study explored how these factors disrupt the individual's commitment to the military and influence their choice to resign from service.

Another important input is the current retention programs in place within the Philippine Marine Corps. These programs are meant to address issues such as career development, job satisfaction, and work-life balance in an effort to prevent turnover. The

study examined whether these programs are effective in retaining personnel or if they fail to address key concerns that would otherwise encourage personnel to stay.

Together, these inputs such as personal experiences, organizational dynamics, and retention strategies serve as the starting point for exploring why personnel decide to leave. These factors were examined through surveys, interviews, and document analysis to understand the underlying motivations and influences that guide the decisions of enlisted personnel.

The process captures the sequential activities undertaken to analyze the inputs and derive meaningful insights. This begins with defining the research problem and establishing a theoretical foundation grounded in the Unfolding Model of Voluntary Turnover. The next phase involves data collection through surveys, interviews, and document analysis, ensuring that both qualitative and quantitative perspectives are captured. This is followed by rigorous data analysis to identify patterns, relationships, and root causes of voluntary turnover. Through the synthesis and interpretation phase, findings are integrated to form a holistic understanding of the factors at play, allowing the study to highlight key areas for intervention.

The output represents the immediate results of these processes, encapsulating the identified causes and contributing factors to voluntary turnover. These findings illuminate the interplay between independent variables, intervening variables, and the dependent variable, emphasizing how factors such as job satisfaction, organizational support, and

career opportunities shape personnel decisions. By systematically addressing these insights, the study identifies critical leverage points for mitigating turnover within the PMC.

Finally, the outcome of the framework focuses on the development of a comprehensive retention program. This program is designed to address the root causes of turnover, proposing targeted solutions such as enhanced support for work-life balance, leadership development initiatives, improved career pathways, and interventions to strengthen camaraderie and unit cohesion. The ultimate goal of the outcome stage is to ensure the retention of enlisted personnel by fostering an organizational environment that aligns with their personal and professional needs, thereby enhancing both individual satisfaction and overall organizational effectiveness.

Integrating the operational framework in this study allows the researcher to establish a coherent and systematic approach to investigating voluntary turnover in the PMC. This approach not only guides the research process but also ensures that actionable solutions are directly informed by the findings of the study, paving the way for meaningful improvements in personnel retention and organizational sustainability.

Study Design

This study followed an explanatory sequential mixed-methods approach to examine the factors influencing voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel of the Philippine Marine Corps (PMC). It began with a quantitative phase, where surveys were conducted to gather

data on personal, professional, and organizational factors affecting personnel decisions. The findings from this stage guided the qualitative phase, which involved in-depth interviews to explore the motivations and experiences of those who left the service. This approach provided both statistical insights and a deeper understanding of individual perspectives.

For data collection, two primary methods were used: surveys and interviews. The quantitative data were gathered through a structured questionnaire featuring Likert-scale items, ensuring consistency in responses. The data were analyzed using weighted mean to interpret trends and assess the significance of various factors. In the qualitative phase, semi-structured interviews were conducted with selected participants from the survey group. These interviews underwent thematic analysis to identify recurring themes and contextualize the survey findings. A review of PMC reports, policies, and personnel records was also undertaken to supplement and validate the data collected from both the survey and interviews.

Study Variables

To comprehensively examine the voluntary turnover of enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps (PMC), it is crucial to define and categorize the key variables that were analyzed. These variables are structured based on the study's conceptual framework to ensure a systematic investigation of their impact on personnel retention.

The variables are grouped into five main categories: Personal Factors, Professional Factors, Organizational Factors, Job-related Stress, and Retention Program

Effectiveness. Each main variable is further broken down into specific indicators or sub-variables that guided data collection and analysis. This categorization allows for a clearer understanding of the various elements influencing voluntary turnover and supports the development of effective retention strategies.

The following table presents a consolidated summary of the study variables:

Table 3. Summary of Study Variables

Main Variable	Type	Indicators or Sub-variables
Personal Factors	Independent	Age, Marital Status, Educational Attainment, Family Responsibilities, Work-Life Balance, Personal Stress Levels, Family Separation, Personal Job satisfaction
Professional Factors	Independent	Years of Service, Professional Job Satisfaction, Job Mismatch, Career Advancement Opportunities, Deployment Impact
Organizational Factors	Independent	Leadership Support, Workplace Culture, Peer Support, Administrative Support, Communication within the Organization
Job-related Stress	Independent	Burnout, Workload and Demands, Psychological Strain
Retention Program Effectiveness	Dependent	Awareness of Retention Programs, Reduction of Voluntary Turnover, Access to Health Care, Perceived Effectiveness of Support Programs

Study Locale

The study were conducted across various regions of the Philippine Marine Corps, focusing on enlisted personnel who have filed for retirement, resignation, or dependency discharge in CY 2025. The personnel are currently stationed in different units and locations throughout the Philippines, including Southern Mindanao, Central Mindanao, Northern Luzon, Palawan, and Manila. Given the widespread distribution of the personnel, the study

aimed to gather insights from different geographical areas, ensuring a diverse representation of experiences related to voluntary turnover within the PMC.

Study Population

The study population consists of 272 enlisted personnel from the Philippine Marine Corps who have filed for retirement, resignation, or dependency discharge in CY 2025. This includes individuals who have opted for optional retirement, are seeking discharge upon expiration of their term of enlistment, or have submitted a resignation request. These personnel are the primary subjects of the study as their decision to leave the service voluntarily is the focus of the research. Since the personnel are scattered across various regions, the study aimed to collect a representative sample from this group.

Samples and Sampling Method

Given the dispersed nature of the study population across various regions in the country, surveying the entire population of enlisted personnel who filed for retirement or resignation was impractical. To ensure a statistically valid yet manageable sample, Slovin's Formula was applied to determine the appropriate survey sample size. With a total population of 272 personnel and a margin of error of 5% ($e = 0.05$), the calculated sample size was 161 personnel.

Applying Slovin's Formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Given:

N=272 (total population of enlisted personnel filing for retirement or resignation)

Margin of error e=0.05 (a common choice for social research)

$$n = \frac{272}{1 + 272 \times (0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{272}{1 + 272 \times 0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{272}{1 + 0.68}$$

$$n = \frac{272}{1.68}$$

$$n = 161.90$$

$$n = 161$$

To select the respondents, a purposive sampling method was used. This approach was chosen to ensure that the sample accurately represented the diverse experiences and motivations behind voluntary turnover. Respondents were intentionally selected from major deployment areas, specifically Southern Mindanao, Central Mindanao, Northern Luzon, Palawan, and Manila, to capture the regional differences in personal, professional, and organizational factors influencing their decisions. This method ensured that insights were gathered from personnel with varying backgrounds and circumstances, providing a well-rounded understanding of voluntary turnover.

For the qualitative component, 35 respondents were selected for in-depth interviews. These interviewees were chosen based on their experiences and circumstances related to voluntary turnover, including optional retirement, resignation, and discharge upon expiration

of enlistment. Interviews were made to those 35 personnel who provided extreme responses in the survey or left comments in the questionnaire. This explanatory sequential design approach allowed for a deeper exploration of survey findings.

To analyze the qualitative data, thematic coding was applied, with respondents highlighting key concerns such as promotion issues, family separation, job-related stress, leadership concerns, reassignment requests, and tattoo policy restrictions. These qualitative insights were cross-referenced with the survey results to establish how different factors acted as shocks that influenced their decision to leave the military service.

Interviews were conducted after at least 40% of the 161 survey responses had been collected. This allowed the researcher to refine the interview questions based on preliminary survey findings, ensuring that the qualitative data provided deeper insights into key themes emerging from the survey responses. The final number of interviewees was determined by data saturation, where no new themes or insights emerged from additional interviews.

Recruitment Plan

After collecting the survey data, the researcher employed a purposive sampling approach to select personnel who provided the most relevant and insightful responses regarding voluntary turnover. To encourage participation in the interviews, the researcher emphasized the importance of their perspectives in shaping a deeper understanding of the issue. Respondents were assured that their insights would contribute to meaningful recommendations for policy improvements within the Philippine Marine Corps. Additionally, confidentiality and anonymity were guaranteed to create a safe environment for open discussions.

Recruitment was conducted through official channels, particularly via Office MC1, which facilitated communication with potential participants. Direct engagement and follow-ups helped address any concerns and reinforced the study's purpose. Consent was obtained not only from the respondents but also from their immediate unit commanders, ensuring compliance with proper protocols. Interviews were then scheduled at times convenient for the participants to accommodate their availability and operational commitments.

Data Gathering Tools & Description

To ensure accuracy and reliability, the researcher validated the survey questionnaire and interview protocol before their official administration. The table below summarizes the data collection tools, the variables covered, the administration process, and the methods of analysis used in this study:

Table 4: Table of Data Gathering Tools

Data Gathering Tools	Variables Covered by the Tool	Administration of the Tool & Respondents Involved	Method for Analysis & Presentation of Results
<p>Survey Questionnaire (25 items, 5-point Likert scale) – Developed by the researcher and pre-tested for reliability (Cronbach’s Alpha = 0.76)</p>	<p>Independent Variables: Personal, professional, and organizational factors affecting turnover</p> <p>Dependent Variable: Likelihood of voluntary turnover</p>	<p>Online administration to 160 respondents selected using Slovin’s formula from a population of 272 personnel who voluntarily filed for retirement or resignation in CY 2025.</p>	<p>Descriptive statistics (weighted mean) to determine trends. Results were cross-referenced with interview findings for deeper interpretation.</p>
<p>Semi-structured Interviews: Conducted with 35 respondents who either provided extreme survey responses or left comments in the questionnaire</p>	<p>Personal and professional experiences, psychological stressors, and organizational concerns (e.g., promotion stagnation, reassignment, tattoo policy, leadership)</p>	<p>One-on-one interviews (virtual) with 35 enlisted personnel from different Marine battalions. Interviews were, transcribed, and anonymized.</p>	<p>Thematic analysis using to identify recurring themes. Findings were compared with survey data for validation.</p>

Surveys

The study employed a structure online survey questionnaire to gather data from respondents. Using Slovin’s formula, a sample size of 161 was determined from the 272 personnel who voluntarily filed for retirement in CY 2025. The survey was distributed online, with responses collected from 160 participants.

The questionnaire was designed to assess personal, professional, and organizational factors affecting voluntary turnover and ways to improve the retention program of PMC . The data analysis utilized descriptive statistics. Specifically weighted mean and average, to identify significant patterns and trends. The data collection process and analysis followed the study's operational framework in order to ensure the alignment with research objectives and methodological rigor.

Interviews

Additionally, interviews were conducted with 35 respondents who provided extreme responses in the survey or left comments in the questionnaire. This explanatory sequential design approach allowed for deeper exploration of survey findings. Thematic coding was applied to analyze qualitative data, with respondents highlighting concerns such as promotion issues, family separation, stress on the job, leadership concerns, reassignment requests, and tattoo policy restrictions. These qualitative insights were cross-referenced with survey results to establish how different factors such as promotion concerns, reassignment preferences, and job stress acted as shocks (referring to significant events or experiences that cause employees to reassess their commitment to an organization and may lead to voluntary turnover, which can be positive (e.g., receiving a better job offer) or negative (e.g., dissatisfaction with management) and can occur suddenly or accumulate over time) influencing the decision-making process.

Survey Administration and Pre-Testing

The survey questionnaire was reviewed and refined based on feedback from military personnel specialists, the thesis adviser, and senior PMC officers to ensure content and construct validity. A pre-test was conducted among 20 officers (not included in the study sample) who had filed for retirement in CY 2025. The pre-test helped assess the clarity of the questionnaire items. Cronbach's Alpha was used to measure internal consistency, yielding a reliability coefficient of **0.76**, indicating acceptable reliability. The final survey was then administered online, and 160 respondents participated out of the targeted 161.

To enhance credibility, the researcher applied triangulation, cross-referencing interview insights with survey results to identify consistent themes across different ranks, regions, and turnover motivations.

Data Processing and Analysis

A systematic approach was used to analyze both quantitative and qualitative data to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing voluntary turnover among PMC enlisted personnel.

Table 5: Statistical Tool used in Survey Questionnaire

Data Analysis Method	Purpose	Statistical Tools Used
Descriptive Statistics	Identifies trends in voluntary turnover factors (personal, professional, and organizational)	Weighted Mean to measure the impact of each factor

Data Analysis Method	Purpose	Statistical Tools Used
Reliability Testing (Pre-Test)	Assesses internal consistency of survey items	Cronbach's Alpha (0.76) – confirms the survey's reliability
Comparative Analysis	Evaluates response variations across demographic groups	Cross-tabulation and frequency distribution

Table 6: Analysis Tool for Qualitative Data

Stage of Thematic Analysis	Description
Data Transcription	Verbatim transcription of all interview responses
Coding	Initial identification of key phrases and recurring themes. Categorization of themes such as leadership concerns, reassignment requests, promotion stagnation, tattoo policy restrictions and job stress
Pattern Recognition & Interpretation	Linking qualitative themes with survey findings

The interview data underwent thematic analysis, systematically coding responses to identify dominant themes like job satisfaction, leadership support, promotion stagnation, and job-related stress. Patterns such as job mismatch and burnout were prominent, providing deeper insights into turnover decisions.

Qualitative findings were also used to explain survey trends. For instance, if high job stress levels were reported in the survey, interview responses detailed specific stressors such as prolonged deployments, heavy workloads, and limited professional development opportunities. This cross-validation added depth to the study's findings. To enhance reliability, the researcher employed triangulation, aligning survey data with interview insights to validate patterns. This method provided a more complete understanding of

voluntary turnover by combining statistical trends with personal narratives to offer both empirical and experiential evidence.

Ethical Consideration

In conducting research on voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps (PMC), the researcher strictly adhered to ethical standards to maintain the integrity of the study and protect its participants.

Coordination with the PMC was conducted through official channels. The researcher sought authorization from relevant units by formally communicating with the Central Staff, particularly the Staff for Administration and Personnel (MC1), Operations (MC3), and their respective Unit Admin Officers. These communications outlined the purpose of the research, the type of data required, and the planned methods for data collection. The approval of unit commanders was also obtained to facilitate access to personnel while ensuring compliance with institutional protocols.

To uphold informed consent, each participant was provided with a clear explanation of the study's objectives, methodology, and intended use of the findings. The informed consent form explicitly stated that participation was voluntary, with no obligation to continue if they wished to withdraw at any stage. Additionally, participants were assured that their responses would be kept anonymous and that their identities would not be disclosed in any part of the research.

Strict measures were taken to comply with the Data Privacy Law and safeguard the confidentiality of all collected information. Personally identifiable data was not recorded, stored, or linked to specific responses. During data collection, survey responses were stored in a password-protected personal computer of the researcher, accessible only to the researcher. Interview transcripts were anonymized by removing identifying details, and coded using generic identifiers instead of names. In the analysis and reporting of results, only aggregated data and generalized themes were presented, ensuring that no individual responses could be traced back to any participant.

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Introduction

This chapter presents the findings of the study based on the data collected from the survey conducted among enlisted personnel of the Philippine Marine Corps who filed and signified to voluntary leave the military service for CY 2025. The results were analyzed and interpreted to determine the personal, professional, and organizational factors contributing to voluntary turnover. The analysis is anchored based on the research questions, review of related literature, and the overall framework of the study.

The discussion follows a structured approach, beginning with the demographic profile of the respondents followed by the result of the findings and the detailed analysis of key findings in relation to the conceptual framework, operational framework, and existing literature.

Presentation and Interpretation of Data on Profile of Respondents

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing voluntary turnover, it is essential to first examine the demographic characteristics of the respondents. This section provides an overview of their rank distribution, years of service, marital status,

age, and location of last assignment, all of which play a role in the analysis of turnover trends.

Rank Distribution

The rank profile of the respondents indicates that the majority of those who voluntarily left the service were within the middle-enlisted ranks. The distribution is presented in the table and figure below:

Figure 4. Rank Profile of Respondents

The data reveals that the highest percentage of personnel who resigned were Technical Sergeants (44%) and Staff Sergeants (39%). This suggests that mid-career personnel with accumulated experience are more likely to leave the service compared to those at entry-level or senior enlisted positions.

Years of Service

On average, the respondents had served nineteen (19) years in the military before deciding to voluntarily leave the service. This suggests that most personnel leave after

reaching significant tenure, due to retirement eligibility, career stagnation, or dissatisfaction with long-term service conditions. The findings reinforce the importance of shocks to the system, wherein personnel with extended service duration may reconsider their military careers after experiencing pivotal personal or professional events.

Location of the Unit Assignment

The geographical distribution of the respondents' unit assignments provides insight into regional trends in voluntary turnover. The breakdown is presented in figure below:

Figure 5. Location of Unit Headquarters

The data shows that the highest number of resignations came from Southern Mindanao (32%), followed by the Manila-Cavite area (29%). These figures may reflect operational stress, job opportunities outside the service, or family-related factors specific to these locations. The geographical locations or the experience of operational challenges can serve as markers that drive personnel to reconsider their military careers. Others followed like Northern Luzon (18%), Central Mindanao (13%), and Palawan (8%).

Age of Respondents

The average age of the respondents was forty-one (41) years old, indicating that most personnel who voluntarily resigned were in their early forties. This aligns with the observed trend in years of service, as many enlisted personnel nearing two decades of service may begin contemplating career transitions outside the military. This finding further supports the concept of shocks triggering voluntary turnover, particularly as personnel assess their future career prospects and personal priorities.

Marital Status of Respondents

The marital status of the respondents was examined to determine whether family obligations influenced their decision to leave. The distribution is shown in the table below:

Table 7. Marital Status of the Respondents

Marital Status	Count	%
Single	25	16%
Married	133	83%
Widow	2	1%
Total	160	100%

A significant majority of 83% of the respondents were married, suggesting that family responsibilities may have contributed to their decision to leave. This finding notes the high regard for the value on family, as family obligations can act as a major shock influencing the decision-making process of military personnel.

Highest Educational Attainment of Respondents

Survey results on the highest educational attainment of respondents show that 12 personnel (8%) completed high school, 90 personnel (56%) completed K-12 or vocational courses, 51 personnel (32%) completed college, and 7 personnel (4%) pursued postgraduate studies. Analysis of the data reveals that a majority (56%) of the respondents have completed K-12 or vocational education, which suggests that most enlisted personnel entered the military with technical or secondary-level education. A significant proportion (32%) have completed college, indicating a notable percentage of personnel with higher academic qualifications.

Figure 6: Educational Attainment of the Respondents

Presentation of Results and Findings

The succeeding tables and discussions present the results of the quantitative and qualitative data analysis used to identify the factors influencing voluntary turnover. These findings follow the objectives of the study, providing insights into the personal, professional, and organizational factors that contribute to the personnel's decisions to leave the service.

Objective Number 1: Identifying Personal and Professional Factors

Influencing Voluntary Turnover

Table 8; Summary of Quantitative and Qualitative Findings for SO 1

Factor	Quantitative Findings Weighted Mean Average (WMA) and Interpretation	Qualitative Result
Personal Factors		
Family Responsibilities	2.58 (Rarely affects work performance)	However, the interview responses revealed that some personnel suffered emotional and psychological toll of balancing family responsibilities as some of them said that having family responsibilities greatly affect their performance.
	Family responsibilities occasionally cause minor disruptions but are generally manageable. The results indicate that family responsibilities generally have a minimal impact on the ability of enlisted personnel to fulfill their military duties. While occasional disruptions may occur, they are generally manageable and do not significantly hinder operational effectiveness. The relatively low impact of family responsibilities on duty performance may indicate that enlisted personnel have adapted well to the demands of military service, possibly due to their effective coping mechanisms.	
Work-Life Balance	2.94 (Moderate challenge)	Interview responses revealed that there are personnel struggle in balancing personal commitments with unpredictable schedules. While they are generally able to manage their responsibilities, there are instances where fulfilling personal and family obligations requires extra
	The Weighted Mean Average (WMA) of 2.94 indicates that enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps sometimes experience challenges in balancing personal and family commitments outside of work hours.	

Factor	Quantitative Findings Weighted Mean Average (WMA) and Interpretation	Qualitative Result
Stress from Work & Personal Life	<p>2.71 (Sometimes)</p> <p>Personal and work-related demands sometimes lead to significant stress but are not constant. This suggests that personal and work-related demands occasionally lead to significant stress among enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps.</p>	<p>effort or adjustments due to the demands of military service.</p> <p>Mental fatigue due to mission demands and lack of structured support was mentioned by the respondents in the interview. While stress is not a constant issue, there are instances where personnel experience notable pressure due to their responsibilities both at work and in their personal lives.</p>
Family Separation's Impact	<p>2.63 (Moderate influence on turnover)</p> <p>Family separation plays a moderate role in the decision to voluntarily leave the service. The Weighted Mean Average (WMA) of 2.63 suggests that family separation has a moderate influence on the decision of enlisted personnel to voluntarily leave the Philippine Marine Corps.</p>	<p>Missing key family moments is one of the issues mentioned during the interview. Some personnel feel long separations negatively impact their family relations. While it is not the primary reason for leaving, it is a factor that some personnel consider when making career decisions. The results imply that prolonged or frequent time away from family contributes to dissatisfaction among some personnel, particularly those with strong family commitments.</p>
Professional Factors Years of Service	<p>19 years (average)</p> <p>The average years of service of the respondents is 19 years.</p>	<p>Most respondents are senior enlisted personnel, which means that the majority of respondents belong to the experienced, trained senior enlisted personnel.</p>

Factor	Quantitative Findings Weighted Mean Average (WMA) and Interpretation	Qualitative Result
Satisfaction with Current Position	3.86 (Satisfied) The weighted average indicates that most enlisted personnel are generally content with their current position in relation to their professional goals and aspirations. The results suggest that their roles align well with their career expectations and provide them with a sense of fulfillment and professional growth.	However, while the quantitative result indicates a positive result, further analysis of qualitative data from interviews revealed that a number of personnel are not satisfied with their positions due to job mismatch and unmet career expectations.
Job Alignment with Skills & Goals	3.34 (Moderately Match) The result suggests that the position of personnel somewhat matches their skills.	However, interview responses revealed that there is a perception of career stagnation due to job mismatch and underutilized expertise experienced by some of them.
Career Advancement Opportunities	3.82 (Satisfied) The weighted mean average suggests that most enlisted personnel are generally satisfied with the career advancement opportunities available in the Philippine Marine Corps. This indicates that many perceive the system as providing sufficient opportunities for growth and promotion.	However, further qualitative analysis of interview data reveals that some personnel experience frustration due to perceived limitations in advancing their careers. Several respondents expressed concerns about policy-related restrictions and bureaucratic processes that may hinder promotion and professional growth. Bureaucratic hurdles in promotions and reenlistment; limited career opportunity.
Deployments' Impact on Satisfaction	3.52 (Positive impact) Deployments contribute positively to job satisfaction. The weighted mean average of 3.52 indicates that, overall, deployments tend to have a positive impact on job satisfaction for most personnel. Many	However, qualitative data from interviews suggest that while some personnel appreciate the challenges and career benefits that come with deployments, others experience stress and

Factor	Quantitative Findings Weighted Mean Average (WMA) and Interpretation	Qualitative Result
Long Deployments & Turnover Decision	<p>view deployments as opportunities for professional growth, skill enhancement, and operational experience, which contribute to a sense of fulfillment in their roles.</p> <p>3.02 (Moderately influence)</p> <p>Long deployments and family separation moderately influence the decision to leave the military. The weighted mean of 3.02 suggests that long deployments and family separation have a moderate influence on the decision to leave the military service.</p>	<p>fatigue due to prolonged separations from family and the demanding nature of field operations. Some respondents noted that frequent or extended deployments could lead to burnout and impact work-life balance, affecting their overall satisfaction in the long run.</p> <p>While many personnel accept these challenges of long deployment as part of their duty, qualitative data from interviews indicate that prolonged time away from family contributes to emotional strain and dissatisfaction, particularly among those with young children or personal responsibilities at home. Some respondents expressed that the cumulative effect of repeated deployments without sufficient time for family reintegration leads to feelings of detachment and, in some cases, a desire to transition out of service. Frequent rotations contribute to dissatisfaction and eventual resignation.</p>

The analysis of personal and professional factors influencing voluntary turnover in the Philippine Marine Corps reveals a complex interplay between family responsibilities, career aspirations, and military operational demands.

Personal Factors

While family responsibilities and work-life balance pose occasional challenges, they are not the primary reasons for turnover. Many personnel develop coping mechanisms to handle prolonged absences, yet some still experience emotional strain. The quantitative findings indicate that family separation moderately affects turnover decisions (WMA: 2.63), and qualitative insights reveal that missing key family moments is a significant concern for some. Stress from both work and personal life occurs occasionally (WMA: 2.71), with personnel highlighting the need for better mental health support.

Professional Factors

Job satisfaction is relatively high (WMA: 3.86), yet qualitative data points to frustrations regarding job mismatch and career stagnation. While most personnel find their roles rewarding, some feel their expertise is underutilized (WMA: 3.34). Career advancement opportunities are generally perceived positively (WMA: 3.82), but bureaucratic hurdles in the promotion system contribute to dissatisfaction.

Deployments are viewed as career-enhancing (WMA: 3.52), yet qualitative findings indicate that frequent rotations and long absences from family contribute to burnout and resignation. While deployments are essential for skill-building, a lack of adequate rest periods between assignments leads to mental, emotional and physical fatigue.

Family-related concerns, job dissatisfaction due to mismatched roles, and deployment fatigue are significant but varying influences on voluntary turnover. While most

personnel manage these challenges effectively, a segment of the workforce struggles with prolonged separations, career stagnation, and burnout.

Objective Number 2: Identifying Organizational Factors Contributing to Turnover Decisions

Table 9: Summary of Quantitative and Qualitative Findings for SO 2

Factor	Quantitative Findings (Weighted Mean Average - WMA)	Qualitative Findings
Leadership Support and Organizational Factors		
Availability of Leadership Guidance and Resources	3.65 (Moderate support) The weighted mean of 3.65 suggests that leaders often provide clear guidance, necessary resources, and recognition for their personnel's work. This indicates a generally positive leadership approach within the PMC, where most personnel feel supported and acknowledged.	However, qualitative data from interviews reveal that while many leaders uphold strong leadership practices, there are instances where a positive culture and mutual respect are sometimes overlooked in certain units. Some personnel feel unsupported and not being treated with respect by their leaders.
Safety, Teamwork and healthy environment	3.84 (Healthy Environment) The weighted mean of 3.84 suggests that most personnel perceive their unit as maintaining a generally healthy environment in terms of physical safety, teamwork, and communication. This indicates that the majority experience effective coordination and a secure working atmosphere.	However, qualitative data from interviews revealed concerns regarding the perceived diminishing value of senior NCOs within some units. Several respondents expressed frustrations over a growing divide between newly reported second lieutenants and

Factor	Quantitative Findings (Weighted Mean Average - WMA)	Qualitative Findings
Administrative Support, Promotion and Reenlistment Process	<p data-bbox="695 1098 894 1125">3.72 (Satisfied)</p> <p data-bbox="529 1171 1062 1493">The weighted mean of 3.72 indicates that most personnel are generally satisfied with the administrative support and services in the PMC, including promotions, reenlistment, benefits, and overall management. This suggests that these systems are functioning effectively for the majority, meeting expectations in terms of efficiency and accessibility.</p>	<p data-bbox="1089 296 1419 1087">senior NCOs, noting that junior officers often do not seek or heed the advice of more experienced enlisted personnel. This disconnect has led to dissatisfaction among senior NCOs, who feel that their insights and experience are being overlooked. While the overall assessment remains positive, these concerns highlight the need for improved mentorship structures and stronger Officer-NCO relationships to foster a more cohesive and respectful working environment.</p> <p data-bbox="1089 1098 1419 1856">However, qualitative data from interviews highlight certain frustrations, particularly with the reenlistment and promotion processes. Some respondents find the reenlistment process tedious, citing bureaucratic delays and procedural inefficiencies. Additionally, concerns were raised about the fairness of promotion policies, with some Marines expressing that promotions are not equally accessible to all, particularly those with tattoo marks. These</p>

Factor	Quantitative Findings (Weighted Mean Average - WMA)	Qualitative Findings
Communication and Coordination	3.84 (Effective) The weighted mean of 3.84 indicates that communication between different levels of the PMC is generally effective. This suggests that information flow across ranks and units is clear and supports operational coordination.	<p>perceptions suggest that while the administrative system is broadly effective, some Marines perceived that promotions are not equally accessible to all, particularly those with tattoo marks.</p> <p>The absence of adverse comments in interviews reinforces this positive assessment, implying that personnel perceive communication as a functional and reliable aspect of their service..</p>
Culture, shared values, beliefs and norms	3.81 (Positive) The weighted mean of 3.81 indicates that the overall unit culture within the PMC is perceived as positive, fostering teamwork, morale, and a sense of belonging among personnel. This suggests that shared values, beliefs, and norms are generally upheld, contributing to a cohesive working environment.	<p>However, examination of qualitative data revealed that some senior NCOs expressed concerns regarding a perceived decline in mutual respect, particularly in how their ranks and experience are valued. These frustrations highlight potential gaps in leadership dynamics and culture and the need to reinforce professional respect and recognition across different levels of command.</p>
Support from Fellow Marines	3.99 (Good) The weighted mean of 3.99 suggests that Marines generally experience strong support from their peers in terms of teamwork, guidance, and collaboration.	<p>The overall perception is that Marines can rely on each other for support and guidance in fulfilling their duties.</p>

Factor	Quantitative Findings (Weighted Mean Average - WMA)	Qualitative Findings
Job Related Stress	<p data-bbox="943 279 1003 306">2.86</p> <p data-bbox="529 317 769 344">(Stress levels vary)</p> <p data-bbox="529 390 1062 604">Stress levels vary, with a balanced mix of challenging and manageable tasks. The weighted mean of 2.86 indicates that, on average, Marines perceive their current duties as neither overwhelmingly stressful nor completely stress-free.</p>	<p data-bbox="1092 279 1419 930">The qualitative data from interviews support this finding, as responses reflect a mix of experiences with some personnel express concerns about too much workload and pressure, while others consider their responsibilities manageable. This reinforces the idea that stress levels are situational and depend on individual roles, assignments, and personal coping mechanisms.</p>
Workload & Operational Tempo	<p data-bbox="613 940 976 968">3.08 (To a Moderate Extent)</p> <p data-bbox="529 1014 1062 1665">The weighted mean of 3.08 suggests that, on average, the demands of the role such as workload, deployments, and mission expectations have a moderate impact on Marines' decisions to stay or leave the PMC. This means that while these factors influence retention, they are not the sole or overwhelming reason for personnel turnover. Further analysis of the quantitative data shows a mixed experience among Marines. Some personnel find their roles highly demanding, making them consider leaving, while others perceive their workload as manageable and not a decisive factor in their career decisions. This variation results in a neutral overall score.</p>	<p data-bbox="1092 940 1419 1482">The qualitative data from interviews reinforce the quantitative findings, that workload and different role demands affect individuals differently based on their assignments, personal resilience, and long-term career aspirations. There are personnel being overwhelmed by workload and eventually influenced their decision to leave the service.</p>
Burnout, physical, emotional and mental exhaustion	<p data-bbox="613 1675 976 1703">2.65 (Occasionally stressful)</p> <p data-bbox="529 1749 1062 1887">The weighted mean of 2.65 indicates that, on average, Marines sometimes experience burnout in their current roles. This suggests that</p>	<p data-bbox="1092 1675 1419 1887">The qualitative data from interviews reinforce the quantitative findings and suggest that burnout is more prevalent in units or roles with higher</p>

Factor	Quantitative Findings (Weighted Mean Average - WMA)	Qualitative Findings
Influence of Burnout in Voluntary Turnover	<p>burnout is not a constant or widespread issue, but it does occur occasionally among personnel. A deeper look at the quantitative data reveals a mixed experience with some Marines rarely experience burnout, while others encounter it more frequently. This variation results in a score that falls near the middle of the scale.</p> <p>2.65 (Somewhat influences the decision to leave.)</p> <p>The weighted mean of 2.65 suggests that burnout has a moderate influence on Marines' thoughts about leaving the service. This indicates that while burnout does play a role in shaping decisions about retention, it is not the dominant factor for most personnel. Further analysis of the quantitative data shows a mixed response that some Marines report that burnout has little to no effect on their decision to stay or leave, while others feel it has a stronger impact. This variation results in a mid-range quantitative score.</p>	<p>operational tempo, heavier workloads, and prolonged field deployments. Conversely, those in less demanding roles report lower levels of burnout.</p> <p>Based on the interview responses, there are personnel who experienced burn out that led them to leave the service.</p>

Organizational factors, such as promotion policies, workplace culture, and excessive workload demands, further contribute to turnover. The perceived unfairness in the promotion system based on the analysis of qualitative and quantitative data is a primary concern among many respondents, particularly when junior personnel are promoted ahead of their more experienced counterparts. A notable institutional concern discovered in the interview and document analysis by reviewing the existing policies is the **no-tattoo policy** of the Philippine Navy. Many respondents cited this policy as a key reason for opting for early retirement, as it effectively bars them from promotion to higher ranks.

This sentiment is reinforced by **Personnel Directive Number 02**, dated **20 July 2011**, titled *Supplemental Guidelines on the Prohibition/Removal of Tattoo Marks*, and **Personnel Directive Number 04**, dated **17 December 2010**, titled *Policy on the Prohibition/Removal of Tattoo Marks*. Furthermore, the **Outgoing Message Directive Cite: N1-CMB-0424-008**, dated **17 April 2024**, has reiterated and reinforced this restriction. Respondents expressed frustration that despite their service record and qualifications, they were being denied career progression due to a policy that does not directly affect their capabilities and capacity to perform their jobs. This has led to a loss of motivation and a decision among many personnel to retire earlier than planned.

Objective Number 3: Identifying the programs or interventions to effectively address the identified issues and gaps related to voluntary turnover

Table 10: Summary of Quantitative and Qualitative Findings for SO 3

PMC Retention Program	Quantitative Findings - WMA Interpretation	Qualitative Findings
Awareness on the retention program	Majority (73.13%) are aware, but 26.88% are not	Some personnel feel well-informed, while others are unaware of available retention programs
Effectiveness of retention programs	3.13 (Moderately effective) The weighted mean of 3.13 suggests that Marines perceive the current retention programs as moderately effective in addressing their reasons for staying in the PMC. The data reveals a divided perception with some personnel find the programs effective in	Mixed perceptions as some find retention programs helpful, others feel they don't address key concerns like proper career progression to encourage retention.

PMC Retention Program	Quantitative Findings - WMA Interpretation	Qualitative Findings
Accessibility of military healthcare for families	meeting their needs, while others feel they fall short in addressing key concerns 3.06 (Moderately accessible)	Distance to military hospitals and limited availability of services pose challenges are identified during the interview as military treatment facility are limited in the country
Satisfaction with availability and fairness of free housing	2.82 (Moderately satisfied) The weighted mean average of 2.82 indicates that some personnel benefit from housing while others cannot access it due to limited availability.	Limited housing availability and perceptions of unequal distribution create dissatisfaction
Effectiveness of retention programs in addressing financial constraints (e.g., deployment costs)	3.03 (To a Moderate Extent) The weighted mean of 3.03 suggests that the current retention programs somewhat help alleviate financial constraints, particularly regarding deployment costs in remote areas with expensive airfare.	Qualitative data response revealed that high transportation costs for personnel in remote areas are a burden and this support is not accessible to everyone due to limited funds.
Effectiveness of retention programs in addressing organizational factors (e.g., workload, leadership support, job security)	3.20 (Moderate) The weighted mean of 3.20 indicates that the current retention programs address organizational factors such as workload, leadership support, and job security to a moderate extent. This suggests that while some personnel find these programs helpful, there are still noticeable limitations in effectively resolving key organizational concerns.	Workload, long deployment unequal career opportunities, mutual respect and leadership support are recurring concerns discovered during the interview. The interview also revealed that PMC has no institutionalized or published program or policy to enhance retention of personnel.

PMC Retention Program	Quantitative Findings - WMA Interpretation	Qualitative Findings
Supportiveness of administrative systems (e.g., promotions, reenlistment) for career progression	3.36 (Moderately supportive) The weighted mean of 3.36 indicates that while these systems provide some level of assistance, personnel may still encounter challenges in advancing their careers. The score reflects that there are structured processes in place that help facilitate career growth, but gaps remain that could hinder smooth progression.	Delays in promotions and reenlistment were mentioned as issues during the interview with the respondents. It suggest that there is an existing system, it needs to be revisit to be more effective and efficient.

The findings of this study reveal a moderate level of effectiveness of the Philippine Marine Corps' (PMC) retention programs, with varying degrees of success across different factors affecting personnel retention. While awareness of these programs is relatively high (73.13%). The weighted mean of 3.13 suggests that the retention programs are somewhat effective but do not fully address the reasons why personnel choose to stay in the PMC. Qualitative feedback highlights that while career development and benefits are appreciated, concerns regarding work-life balance, stress management, and deployment hardships persist. These concerns indicate the need for revisions to retention strategies, particularly in areas related to mental health support, family welfare, and financial assistance for remote deployments.

Despite a majority being aware of the retention program (3.5 WMA), a significant minority (26.88%) remains uninformed, suggesting that information dissemination needs improvement. Similarly, military healthcare accessibility for personnel families (3.06 WMA) reflects logistical challenges, particularly in remote areas. This reinforces the need

for better communication strategies, telemedicine services, and enhanced partnerships with civilian hospitals to provide comprehensive healthcare solutions.

The 2.82 WMA for free housing indicates noticeable dissatisfaction, mainly due to availability and fairness concerns. Qualitative data shows that perceived unequal access to housing opportunities creates discontent among Marines. A more transparent housing allocation system and rental assistance programs could mitigate this issue. Additionally, financial constraints related to deployment (3.03 WMA) remain a significant factor affecting retention. The qualitative responses highlight that high airfare costs for remote deployments pose a burden, suggesting a need for expanded financial aid packages or travel subsidies.

Personnel believe that retention programs partially address organizational concerns such as workload, leadership support, and job security (3.20 WMA). However, leadership inconsistencies and workload imbalances still pose challenges. Qualitative responses reinforce the necessity for enhanced leadership training, feedback mechanisms, and improved workload distribution.

Regarding career progression, administrative processes for promotions and reenlistment received a moderate WMA of 3.36. Marines expressed frustration over delays and lack of transparency in promotions, which impacts morale and career motivation. Addressing these concerns requires streamlined promotion and reenlistment procedures, ensuring a fair and merit-based system that supports long-term retention.

In assessing the effectiveness of the retention policy of the PMC, gaps were identified regarding accessibility, fairness and integration of program which require strategic and policy intervention. This is probably attributed to the fact that PMC has no published or institutionalized retention program. Interview with Office MC1 revealed that while housing

benefits, travel allowance also known as Rest and Recreation Fund to support travel expenses of personnel and free military healthcare as part of the benefits being made available to the members of the PMC to encourage retention of personnel and can be considered as part of retention policy or program, the PMC has indeed no published policy or plan to fully integrate the program.

Table 11: Thematic Analysis of Qualitative Response

Theme	Sub-Theme	Participant ID	Excerpt of Responses
1. MILITARY POLICIES	Bureaucratic Challenges in Reenlistment	R2, R11, R19	"The reenlistment process feels excessive, especially the mid-term reenlistment." "There's no sense of career progress, making service less fulfilling." "The process of reenlistment should be streamlined; it sometimes feels discouraging."
	Promotion System & Career Advancement	R1, R2, R4, R6, R8, R35	"One of the biggest reasons many resign is the promotion system." "It is concerning when juniors are promoted and get career courses ahead of us." "Since we can no longer be promoted due to policy, there's no reason to stay in service." "Not being selected for career courses limits our chances of promotion."
2. UNIT ASSIGNMENTS AND MORALE	Job Mismatch & Career Specialization	R3, R9, R14	"I am a mortarman who was reassigned to an infantry battalion." "Going back to the infantry caused confusion and dissatisfaction." "The Corps

Theme	Sub-Theme	Participant ID	Excerpt of Responses
3. FAMILY CONCERNS	Decline in Respect for Senior NCOs	R7, R11, R17, R2, R32	needs to consider personnel specialization when assigning duties." "The Marine Corps has changed, it's not like before when everyone, including officers, showed respect to senior NCOs." "Disrespect from junior officers affects morale." "If new 2LTs do not listen, it causes division and weakens teamwork."
	Emotional Strain Due to Family Separation	R1, R2, R5, R10, R18, R22, R30, R31	"Even if your family is nearby, it still feels like they're far away because of the workload." "As a senior, I wanted to be closer to my family." "My spouse has to handle everything alone, which is a heavy burden."
	Family Obligations & Personal Crises	R9, R10, R18, R28	"My child got sick, and all our savings were depleted." "I need to be present and witness my child's growth." "Sudden changes in deployment are also difficult because you don't have enough time to settle your personal matters."
4. LOCATION OF DEPLOYMENT	Distance from Family & Work-Life Balance	R1, R17, R10, R13, R20, R9	"Distant assignments significantly affect morale." "When we are far from our family, we tend to feel more frustrated and stressed." "It affects my motivation. If I'm always far away, I feel like I have no work-life balance."
	Remote Deployment and Fatigue	R11, R14, R16	"Distant assignments have a significant impact, especially when soldiers are far from their families." "When the assignment is

Theme	Sub-Theme	Participant ID	Excerpt of Responses
5. WORK-RELATED CHALLENGES	Work-Related Exhaustion & Stress	R1, R17, R10, R13, R20, R9	far, we feel exhausted and face additional expenses." "There's often a manpower shortage, so the workload doubles." "Some of my colleagues say they're exhausted and just want to leave so they can be with their families." "It affects my motivation."
	Stress and Distraction at Work	R7, R11, R17, R2, R32	"If there is no proper respect and fair treatment, we lose trust in our leaders." "It's difficult to stay in an organization where mutual respect is lost." "Low morale due to poor leadership leads to distraction at work."
6. JOB SATISFACTION & CAREER GROWTH	Lack of Job Satisfaction & Motivation	R1, R11, R19, R2	"When you're not happy with what you're doing, you start losing motivation." "I lose my drive, which leads to exhaustion and burnout." "There's no career progress, making service less fulfilling."
	Reassignments & Career Disruptions	R3, R5, R6, R7, R26, R34, R35	"Sudden reassignment to Battalion." "I was suddenly reassigned to Northern Luzon. I am from Zamboanga and was previously assigned in Zamboanga City." "The reassignment policy needs to be more predictable."
7. SUGGESTED INTERVENTIONS TO IMPROVE RETENTION	Family oriented deployment Policy. Residence Based.	R12, R13, R16, R2, R5, R9, R20, R21, R22, R24, R30, R31, R32	"If assignments were closer to home, life would be more balanced." "Our job as soldiers is very difficult, so if there is an opportunity to be stationed closer to our

Theme	Sub-Theme	Participant ID	Excerpt of Responses
	Leadership & Organizational Culture	R7, R11, R17, R2, R32	families, it would be a great help for our mental and emotional well-being." "Soldiers need to be assigned to units closer to their residence." "If there is no proper respect and fair treatment, we lose trust in our leaders." "Fair promotion opportunities and leadership respect can improve retention." "The organization should ensure fair career advancement opportunities."

Analysis of Qualitative Data

The responses gathered from the participants highlight key factors influencing voluntary turnover in the Philippine Marine Corps. These factors revolve around military policies, assignments, family concerns, deployment locations, work-related exhaustion, job satisfaction, and potential interventions to improve retention.

One of the most pressing concerns raised is the bureaucratic challenges in reenlistment and promotion policies. Several participants expressed frustration over the complexities of the reenlistment process, describing it as discouraging and unnecessary. Likewise, dissatisfaction with the promotion system emerged as a recurring issue. Many felt that promotion opportunities were limited or unfair, particularly when junior personnel were promoted ahead of more experienced Marines. The lack of career advancement and

perceived inequities in professional development contributed to a sense of stagnation, making some personnel question their long-term commitment to service.

Another significant theme relates to military assignments and morale. Several respondents voiced concerns about job mismatches, where personnel with specialized skills were reassigned to unrelated roles, leading to dissatisfaction and decreased motivation. Additionally, some senior personnel noted a decline in the traditional respect shown to non-commissioned officers (NCOs), with younger officers displaying a lack of regard for seniority and experience. This erosion of respect was seen as a contributing factor to low morale and frustration within the ranks.

Family concerns and deployment locations also played a critical role in personnel decisions to leave the service. Many respondents spoke about the strain caused by prolonged separation from their families, which made balancing personal and professional responsibilities extremely difficult. Emotional stress was further compounded by the financial burden of managing a household while stationed far from home. Some Marines cited personal crises, such as a child's illness, as moments when they realized the challenges of military life outweighed the benefits.

Furthermore family separation, distance and work-related exhaustion emerged as key stressors. Some Marines felt that distant deployments led to increased fatigue, financial strain, and reduced motivation. Others mentioned that the heavy workload, combined with a lack of manpower, contributed to burnout. The inability to properly rest or take time off further aggravated stress levels, affecting both personal well-being and professional performance.

Job satisfaction and career growth were also recurrent concerns. Some participants expressed frustration over the lack of fulfillment in their current assignments, while others pointed out that frequent reassignments disrupted their professional development. Sudden transfers, particularly to unfamiliar or remote areas, left many feeling disconnected from both their work and their long-term goals within the organization.

Given these challenges, several suggested interventions to improve retention were brought forward. Many emphasized the need for policy reforms, particularly in assignment policies, reenlistment procedures, and promotion systems. A common recommendation was for personnel to be assigned to units closer to their place of residence, which would improve work-life balance and morale. Others highlighted the importance of maintaining a strong leadership culture built on mutual respect and fairness, as well as providing clear career progression pathways to keep personnel motivated and engaged. The findings suggest that voluntary turnover in the Philippine Marine Corps is driven by a combination of structural, professional, and personal factors. And in developing and institutionalizing a Retention Program of PMC, all these things should be considered.

CHAPTER 4

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents a summary of the study and the subsequent conclusion based on the findings of the gathered data and the recommendations. The study examined the personal, professional, and organizational factors influencing voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel of the Philippine Marine Corps and assessed the effectiveness of existing retention programs. The respondents were 160 enlisted personnel who voluntarily filed for separation from service in CY 2025.

Summary of Findings and Analysis

The study sought the answers to the following questions:

1. What personal and professional factors, including job satisfaction, that influence voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps?
2. What organizational factors, such as leadership support and job-related stress, contribute to turnover decisions?

3. What types of programs or interventions can effectively address the identified issues and gaps related to voluntary turnover?

The study was conducted from November 2024 to March 2025 and used an explanatory sequential design, where quantitative data were collected and analyzed first, followed by qualitative data to provide deeper context and insights and document analysis. The research instruments included a structured survey questionnaire and semi structured interview, while the sampling design applied purposive sampling and used Slovin's formula to determine the sample size.

The first research question sought to analyze the personal and professional factors influencing voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel. The survey results revealed that 83% of the respondents were married, highlighting that family responsibilities played a major role in their decision to leave. Work-life balance was rated at 2.94, indicating moderate difficulty in balancing military service with personal obligations. Interview responses reinforced this finding, as several Marines expressed frustration over missing important family events due to prolonged deployments. The average age of respondents was 41 years old, and the average years of service before resignation was 19 years, suggesting that turnover was more prevalent among mid-career personnel.

Job satisfaction had a weighted mean of 3.86, suggesting that while some personnel were content with their jobs, a significant number experienced dissatisfaction. Job mismatch was also a concern, scoring 3.34, with interview findings revealing that Marines were sometimes assigned to positions that did not match their skills and expertise.

The second research question examined the organizational factors contributing to voluntary turnover. Organizational shocks, particularly sudden reassignments, were identified as a major factor. Some personnel were unexpectedly transferred to distant units, making it difficult to adjust and causing additional financial and emotional strain. Promotion-related concerns were also a recurring theme, with the Philippine Navy's no-tattoo policy being a significant institutional shock. Many Marines expressed frustration that this policy blocked their promotions despite their qualifications, leading them to consider early retirement.

Workplace culture and leadership concerns were also identified as key organizational factors. Survey findings showed that job-related stress had a weighted mean of 2.71, while burnout scored 2.65, indicating that stress and exhaustion were persistent but not extreme issues. Some interviewees reported that respect for senior enlisted personnel had declined, contributing to a weakened sense of unit cohesion.

The third research question focused on the effectiveness of existing retention programs. The survey revealed that 73.13% of respondents were aware of the PMC's retention program, yet its perceived effectiveness was only moderate, with a weighted mean of 3.13. Housing and healthcare benefits were identified as areas needing improvement. The satisfaction rating for housing benefits was 2.82, indicating that while some personnel benefited from available housing, many faced challenges related to fairness and accessibility. Healthcare accessibility was rated at 3.06, suggesting that while medical services were available, logistical challenges and distance made access difficult for many Marines stationed in remote areas.

Financial support programs were found to be insufficient, particularly for personnel deployed to remote locations with high transportation costs. The survey recorded a weighted mean of 3.03 for financial assistance, indicating that while some support was provided, gaps remained that placed additional financial burdens on personnel. Career progression policies were rated at 3.36, with many respondents highlighting frustrations over promotion and career course delays and tedious reenlistment process

The findings of the study suggest that voluntary turnover in the Philippine Marine Corps is influenced by a combination of personal, professional, and organizational factors. Family responsibilities, job mismatch, organizational shocks such as sudden reassignments and the no-tattoo policy, and inadequate retention programs were identified as primary reasons for personnel resignations. The study further revealed that while there is existing program to encourage retention, there is no articulated policy to integrate all these initiatives into a complemented and comprehensive program to maximize its intended benefits of encouraging everyone to remain in the service. While existing initiatives to encourage retention offer some support, their effectiveness remains moderate due to gaps in implementation and accessibility and the absence of a clear program to align these initiatives, with these findings policy interventions are recommended to improve retention.

A multi-faceted approach is needed to address the issues contributing to voluntary turnover in the Philippine Marine Corps. Personal and professional factors, such as job satisfaction and alignment of assignments with individual strengths, must be given priority. Simultaneously, organizational issues, particularly leadership support and the reduction of job-related stress, must be addressed through reforms and interventions. The PMC should

prioritize programs that ensure career progression is based on merit, respect, and transparency, while also creating a supportive environment that promotes well-being and addresses the unique challenges of military life.

Conclusion

The following are the concluding statements:

1. Personal and professional factors that influence voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps (PMC) include job satisfaction, career advancement opportunities, and work-life balance. Enlisted personnel who feel their efforts are not adequately recognized or rewarded may experience dissatisfaction, leading them to seek opportunities elsewhere. Limited promotion prospects, lack of professional development, and unclear career paths are significant deterrents, as they feel their potential is stunted within the organization. Furthermore, personal factors such as family considerations, health issues, or a desire for more time with loved ones can also lead to voluntary turnover, particularly when deployments are far from home or involve long periods of separation.

Another contributing factor is job-related stress and the demanding nature of military life. Enlisted personnel often face intense physical and mental stress, which can lead to burnout if not addressed adequately. The lack of sufficient support systems or leadership that values their well-being can exacerbate this issue. Additionally, issues related to the work

environment, such as strained relationships with superiors or peers and lack of mutual respect and recognition for their contributions, can demoralize personnel and drive them to consider leaving the service. These personal and professional factors intertwine, creating a complex landscape where dissatisfaction with both career progression and personal well-being leads to voluntary turnover.

2. Organizational factors, such as leadership support, play a significant role in the turnover decisions of enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps (PMC). Leaders who fail to provide guidance, recognition, or support can create a toxic work environment that fosters dissatisfaction. When personnel feel their leaders are unapproachable, unfair, or uninvolved in their development, it weakens trust and morale, ultimately driving them to seek alternatives outside the military. Furthermore the lack of transparent communication and acknowledgment of achievements can demotivate personnel, reducing their commitment to stay in the service. Effective leadership is vital in promoting job satisfaction, fostering a sense of belonging, and mitigating feelings of isolation or resentment that could lead to voluntary turnover.

Job-related stress is another critical organizational factor contributing to turnover decisions. The demanding nature of military life, including long hours, physical strain, and the emotional toll of frequent deployments, can lead to burnout. When stressors are not adequately managed through proper resources, training, or support systems, enlisted personnel can feel overwhelmed that ultimately affect their decision to remain in the service.

If the organization fails to provide sufficient mental health resources, opportunities for stress management, or a healthy work-life balance, personnel may experience fatigue and disengagement, which can prompt them to leave the military. Both leadership and job-related stress, when not effectively addressed, significantly contribute to the turnover intentions of enlisted personnel in the PMC.

3. To address the personal-professional factors contributing to voluntary turnover, the Philippine Marine Corps (PMC) can implement a comprehensive professional development program that ensures career progression, skill development, and job satisfaction. This program could include mentorship initiatives, career planning sessions, and transparent communication about promotion opportunities. The PMC should also invest in continuous training and providing a clear path for advancement. This can help enlisted personnel feel valued and see a future within the organization. Implementing flexible deployment schedules or family oriented deployment programs could help balance personal and professional lives that stress and the desire to leave the service. Financial assistance programs for healthcare and transportation cost during travel should be programmed to further enhance job satisfaction and alleviate some of the pressures that contribute to turnover.

On the organizational side, addressing leadership support and job-related stress is crucial in reducing voluntary turnover. Leadership training programs that focus on empathy, communication, and fair treatment can foster better relationships between officers and enlisted personnel, improving morale and trust. To mitigate job-related stress, the PMC can

create wellness programs that focus on mental health, stress management, and resilience training. Providing support for families during deployments, such as family counseling services online can also reduce stress for personnel. A more supportive and inclusive work environment, with clear policies for addressing grievances and promoting work-life balance will also contribute to greater retention.

Recommendations

Overview and Innovation Program

In addressing the persistent challenge of voluntary turnover among enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps (PMC), this study proposes a Comprehensive Retention and Career Development Program designed to mitigate key factors influencing voluntary turnover. This innovation program is grounded in empirical findings from this research, integrating targeted interventions with the goal to synchronize all the initiatives currently in place to enhance job satisfaction, address job mismatch, support mental health, and improve family-work balance. The integration of the PMC's retention efforts can foster long-term commitment and career fulfillment among Marines and expected to achieve better results.

To ensure the successful implementation of this innovation, an effective communication and promotion plan is essential. This includes a phased rollout strategy that involves high-level briefings for key decision-makers, unit-level awareness campaigns, and direct engagement with enlisted personnel. Multiple platforms, such as official PMC directives, digital communication channels, and face-to-face dialogues, will be used to

disseminate program details and encourage buy-in from both leadership and rank-and-file personnel.

The Retention Program that will be developed by the PMC will not just integrate the existing retention initiatives but also include the following strategic goals to address the identified gaps related to voluntary turnover.

1. Enhance Career Development and Advancement Opportunities: Implement structured mentorship programs, career development workshops, and transparent promotion pathways to ensure enlisted personnel see a clear trajectory for growth within the PMC. Regular feedback on career goals, skill development, and potential for advancement will help boost job satisfaction and motivation.

To resolve job mismatch and dissatisfaction, a Career Alignment and Progression System should be created and institutionalized. This system should require the Marine Corps to have a Personnel Management Center, under the Career Management Branch of Office MC1, to conduct a biennial skills assessment of enlisted personnel and match assignments based on expertise involving all Units Admin and Personnel Officer. A mandatory career counseling program should be implemented to ensure that Marines receive guidance on career tracks, promotion eligibility, and specialized training opportunities. The Career Assignment and Progression System needs to develop a repository of skills and training that personnel has to follow throughout their career and track the unit assignment of personnel to ensure that it aligns well with their training and expertise. Office MC1 is recommended to review restrictive policies, particularly the no-tattoo rule, and determine if modifications can be made without compromising service regulations. If possible, restriction policy

regarding Tattoo should have no retroactive effect. This means that soldiers who have tattoo before the publication of the policy should not be affected by the policy.

2. Improve Work-Life Balance: Introduce more flexible deployment schedules and family support programs, which could include offering financial assistance for family-related needs, such as healthcare or transportation cost annually to family who is being deployed in a very remote areas that require excessive transportation cost. The Philippine Marine Corps can schedule a family time annually to enable the dependents to visit the deployment area of soldiers and enjoy family day that would allow dependents to interact with their love ones and their fellow dependents. This initiative can be undertaken using the military aircraft and military ships as their mode of transportation. Undertaking this program will not only enhance the morale of personnel and their dependents but also allow the families to understand the very nature of the job of the PMC personnel and their working environment. It will also encourage and brings opportunity for a bigger social support from their fellow dependents that they could meet during the family day.

The Philippine Marine Corps can also establish a Family Stability and Support Policy through a formal directive. This policy should include priority assignment consideration for personnel serving in a very remote areas for a very long time, rotational deployment planning should be encouraged to ensure Marines are not continuously assigned to distant locations. Monitoring of unit assignment and proposal to conduct rotational deployment should be included as one of the jobs of Unit Admin Officers to be submitted quarterly to higher headquarters. Unit Commanders through their Admin Officers should also be required to submit quarterly reports on family-related concerns to ensure that family welfare is considered in personnel assignments.

3. **Leadership Training and Support:** Launch leadership development programs focused on enhancing emotional intelligence, empathy, and communication skills among officers and enlisted personnel. Training leaders to be more supportive and understanding of enlisted personnel's needs will build trust, improve morale, and reduce turnover. Officers should also be trained in conflict resolution and fairness to address any grievances promptly and effectively.

4. **Stress Management and Mental Health Support:** Establish programs that focus on mental health and stress management, including counseling services and resilience training for both personnel and their families. Providing mental health lectures and promoting a culture of openness and support for mental well-being will reduce job-related stress and burnout.

To mitigate organizational shocks such as sudden reassignments and restrictive promotion policies, an Advance Reassignment and Rotation Policy should be established. A standardized 90-day notification period for reassignment should be mandated, except for urgent operational needs.

5. **Foster an Inclusive and Supportive Organizational Culture:** Promote a culture that values mutual respect, fairness, and inclusion, especially among different ranks. Senior leadership should emphasize the importance of showing respect for all members, regardless of rank or position, and create systems for handling grievances and addressing issues related to respect and unfair treatment.

To improve leadership engagement and workplace culture, Leadership lectures and program should be scheduled quarterly to be undertaken by all Marine Units. This program should include quarterly leadership effectiveness evaluations of officers and senior enlisted personnel, integrating personnel feedback into promotion and command assignments. Unit Sgt Majors should be responsible for conducting mentorship programs monthly to that NCOs remains engaged in personnel development.

6. In terms of Housing and Healthcare, given the significant resources required, this should be a long-term goal. The Philippine Marine Corps should gradually revise its Housing and Benefits Policy to establish clear and transparent criteria for housing benefits to be provided to personnel and ensure fair distribution based on tenure and operational needs. On base housing in different PMC camps should be gradually programmed in the APB if possible. Likewise, improving healthcare access through a private healthcare providers should be studied for its feasibility. This will allow the PMC to assess if they can provide this benefits to the personnel and their dependents.

Thus the Researcher is recommending this Comprehensive Retention and Career Development Program with the proposed initiatives and timeline that will be discussed in succeeding paragraphs.

**COMPREHENSIVE RETENTION PROGRAM FOR THE PHILIPPINE MARINE
CORPS (PMC) TARGETING PERSONAL-PROFESSIONAL AND
ORGANIZATIONAL FACTORS TO REDUCE
VOLUNTARY TURNOVER**

Objective: To develop a comprehensive retention program that addresses both personal-professional and organizational factors contributing to voluntary turnover in the

Philippine Marine Corps (PMC). The program aims to provide evidence-based strategies to reduce turnover by enhancing career satisfaction, improving organizational culture, providing professional development opportunities, and fostering well-being among personnel.

Table 12: List of Innovation, Objectives and Timeframe

Innovation Area	Objectives	List of Innovations	Timeframe of Implementation
Career Development and Advancement Opportunities	Ensure clear career progression pathways that enhance job satisfaction and professional growth, fostering long-term commitment to the PMC.	Develop personalized Career Pathways: Digital tool for tracking career growth and setting goals. Career Alignment and Progression System: Regular Career Counseling and Mentorship. Clear Promotion and Advancement Criteria: Transparent, merit-based promotion system with regular career counseling. Review of Restrictive Policy - No tattoo Policy	6-12 months
Work Life Balance and Morale and Welfare	Improve overall work life balance among PMC personnel and its dependent and widen social and peer support	Conduct of Family day Annually Family Stability and Support Policy through family oriented deployment procedure and rotational deployment scheme.	6-12 months

Innovation Area	Objectives	List of Innovations	Timeframe of Implementation
Leadership Training and Support	Improve leadership practices and increase trust in senior leadership to ensure service members feel supported and valued.	Leadership Training and Accountability Lecture: Mandatory leadership education and mentorship quarterly. Leadership Feedback: Open feedback system for evaluating leadership effectiveness of Officers and NCOs Mentoring: Leadership Mentoring by Sgt Major Semi-annually.	6-12 months
Stress Management and Mental Support	To enhance personnel well-being by providing consistent mental health support, stress management, and resources to help personnel cope with the demands of military life	Conduct of Quarterly Mental health and Stress Counselling to personnel and dependents. Advance Reassignment and Rotation Policy - 90 day Rule	3-6 months
Organizational Culture	To foster a positive organizational culture characterized by respect, fairness, and transparency, which enhances trust and cohesion among all ranks.	Quarterly leadership Forum between Officers and Senior NCOs	3-6 months
Housing and Healthcare	To improve the quality of life for PMC personnel by enhancing access to housing and healthcare benefits.	Inclusive Housing benefits (on Base and Off base) Access to Private health care providers	3-7 years

Change Plan for the Comprehensive Retention Program

This plan outlines a phased approach to implementing key innovations aimed at improving personnel retention in the Philippine Marine Corps (PMC). The initiatives are categorized into Career Development and Advancement Opportunities, Work-Life Balance, Leadership Training, Stress Management, Organizational Culture, and Housing & Healthcare.

Each innovation follows a structured timeline as follows:

Immediate Desired Outcomes (1-12 months): Policy formulation, feasibility studies, and initial program development.

Medium-Term Desired Outcomes (1-3 years): Implementation of policies and programs.

Long-Term Desired Outcomes (3+ years): Institutionalization, evaluation, and refinement of programs and policies.

Table 13: Innovation with Outcome Matrix

Innovation Area	Innovation	Immediate Outcomes (1-12 months)	Medium-Term Outcomes (1-3 years)	Long-Term Outcomes (3+ years)
Career Development and Advancement Opportunities	Personalized Career Pathways (Digital Career Tracking)	Develop and publish a directive on career tracking.	Implementation of digital tool for career tracking.	Institutionalization and integration into personnel management system.
	Career Alignment & Progression System (Mentorship, Counseling)	Establish mentorship program framework.	Implement career counseling sessions and mentorship system.	Continuous assessment and refinement of mentorship programs.

Innovation Area	Innovation	Immediate Outcomes (1-12 months)	Medium-Term Outcomes (1-3 years)	Long-Term Outcomes (3+ years)
Work-Life Balance, Morale, and Welfare	Clear Promotion and Advancement Criteria	Review and update promotion policies.	Implement transparent, merit-based promotion system.	Institutionalize policy with periodic evaluations.
	Review of Restrictive Policy – No Tattoo Policy	Conduct policy review and feasibility study.	Implement changes (if approved) and provide guidance.	Evaluate effects on recruitment and retention.
	Conduct of Family Day Annually	Publish directive for annual family day.	First cycle of family day conducted and assessed.	Family day institutionalized as an annual event.
	Family Stability & Support Policy (Family-Oriented Deployment & Rotational Deployment)	Conduct feasibility study and develop policy recommendations	Implement pilot rotational deployment scheme.	Evaluate and refine policy for full implementation.
Leadership Training and Support	Leadership Training & Accountability Lecture	Develop and implement quarterly leadership education sessions.	Regular monitoring and adjustments based on feedback.	Institutionalized as part of officer and NCO education.
	Leadership Feedback System	Develop policy and mechanism for open feedback.	Conduct pilot testing of feedback system.	Full implementation and integration into performance evaluations.
	Leadership Mentoring by Sgt Major (Semi-Annual)	Establish mentoring program structure and schedule.	First cycle of mentoring sessions completed.	Integrated into leadership development strategy.
Stress Management	Quarterly Mental Health	Establish framework and engage mental	Conduct first cycles of	Institutionalized as an ongoing program.

Innovation Area	Innovation	Immediate Outcomes (1-12 months)	Medium-Term Outcomes (1-3 years)	Long-Term Outcomes (3+ years)
and Mental Support	& Stress Counseling Advanced Reassignment & Rotation Policy (90-Day Rule)	health professionals. Conduct policy review and feasibility study.	counseling sessions. Pilot test and refine policy.	Fully integrated into personnel management.
Organizational Culture	Quarterly Leadership Forum (Officers & Senior NCOs)	Publish directive and guidelines for forums.	Conduct forums and gather feedback for improvement.	Institutionalized as a standard leadership engagement mechanism.
Housing and Healthcare	Inclusive Housing Benefits (On-Base & Off-Base) Access to Private Healthcare Providers	Conduct feasibility study on housing expansion. Conduct policy review and partnership feasibility study.	Implement initial housing program for select personnel. Implement pilot program for private healthcare access.	Full implementation and assessment of housing impact. Evaluate and integrate into long-term healthcare policy.

Shown in the Figure below is the Gantt Chart reflecting the List of Innovations and the Timeline:

Figure 7: Gantt Chart of Implementing Innovations

ADDRESSING RESISTANCE TO CHANGE

Implementing innovations within the Philippine Marine Corps follows a structured and hierarchical approach where directives ensure compliance. However, for long-term success, it is essential to address potential resistance by promoting understanding and acceptance. In every organization, change is often met with skepticism, particularly when it alters established norms, routines, or policies affecting career progression, work-life balance, leadership structures, and personnel welfare. While Marines are trained to follow orders, ensuring that these innovations are perceived as beneficial rather than bureaucratic changes will enhance their effectiveness and sustainability. A well-planned change management strategy must focus on clear communication, leadership involvement, phased implementation, and continuous assessment.

To achieve this, every innovation must be introduced with a clear rationale and a structured plan that allows personnel to adjust. Leaders at all levels play a crucial role in reinforcing the value of these changes by serving as role models and advocates of these

initiatives. Transparency in policy development, pilot programs, and active feedback mechanisms will help address concerns before they escalate into resistance. The table below outlines specific approaches in managing resistance for each innovation to ensure acceptance and long-term institutionalization.

Table 14: Approaches in Managing Resistance

Innovation	Potential Resistance	Approach to Address Resistance
Personalized Career Pathways (Digital Career Tracking) Career Alignment & Progression System (Mentorship, Counseling)	Skepticism about digital tracking tools and their impact on promotions. Perceived additional workload for mentors.	Conduct briefings to explain how the system enhances career planning. Integrate mentorship responsibilities into leadership duties and recognize outstanding mentors.
Clear Promotion and Advancement Criteria	Concerns over fairness and transparency.	Conduct regular briefings, publish clear guidelines, and allow for feedback.
Review of Restrictive Policy – No Tattoo Policy	Resistance from traditionalists who view tattoos as unprofessional.	Present findings from feasibility studies showing recruitment and retention benefits.
Conduct of Family Day Annually	Possible perception of non-essential activity. Logistically heavy activity	Demonstrate its impact on morale through pilot events and feedback. Encourage support from Senior Leaders
Family Stability & Support Policy (Family-Oriented Deployment & Rotational Deployment)	Concerns over operational readiness.	Implement pilot programs and assess impact on unit readiness

Innovation	Potential Resistance	Approach to Address Resistance
Leadership Training & Accountability Lecture	Resistance to additional training requirements.	Integrate into existing PME (Professional Military Education) framework.
Leadership Feedback System	Skepticism about fairness and confidentiality.	Conduct initial pilot phase with voluntary participation and anonymous submissions.
Leadership Mentoring by Sgt Major (Semi-Annual)	Perception of redundancy with other training programs.	Align with leadership development programs and highlight career benefits.
Quarterly Mental Health & Stress Counseling	Stigma around seeking mental health support.	Normalize discussions on mental resilience and involve senior personnel in participation.
Advanced Reassignment & Rotation Policy (90-Day Rule)	Perception of being not flexible for rotation and reassignment	Communicate the benefits and discuss the rationale of the policy
Quarterly Leadership Forum (Officers & Senior NCOs)	Viewed as redundant if discussions do not lead to action.	Ensure follow-through on key discussion points and communicate outcomes.
Inclusive Housing Benefits (On-Base & Off-Base)	Concerns cost and expenses in constructing on base housing	Communicate to everyone that the decision to provide housing is based on a comprehensive feasibility study
Access to Private Healthcare Providers		

Communication Plan: Getting Support for the Comprehensive Program

To effectively implement the proposed innovations, a structured communication plan is necessary to ensure that all relevant offices and personnel are informed, engaged, and aligned with the objectives of these changes. The process begins by furnishing a copy of this study to the Office of MC1, which oversees personnel management and career development, as well as to MC3 for operational considerations and MC8 for education and training. Their review and endorsement will provide the necessary institutional backing and allow for coordination on the issuance of directives, feasibility studies, and policy adjustments. Once

these key offices have provided their inputs, an official directive will be drafted and disseminated through the chain of command to ensure compliance and clarity on implementation timelines.

Following the publication of directives, communication will extend to Unit Commanders and key personnel through briefings, workshops, and leadership forums to explain the rationale and expected benefits of each innovation. Digital platforms and traditional communication systems will be used to distribute updates and gather feedback and ensure transparency. Pilot programs and initial implementation phases will be closely monitored, with results communicated back to all stakeholders to demonstrate progress and address concerns. The table below outlines the specific communication strategies tailored to each innovation area to achieve awareness, understanding, and buy-in across all levels of the organization.

Table 15: Communication Strategy

Target Audience	Communication Objective	Communication Method	Responsible Person/Office	Timeframe
MC1, MC3, MC8	Secure endorsement and integration of innovations into HPMC policies.	Submission of study and policy recommendations.	Study Proponent	Month 1
Marine Corps Headquarters	Approval and dissemination of directives.	Official directive and Outgoing Dispatch.	MC1, MC3, MC8	Month 2-3
Unit Commanders & Key Staff	Ensure understanding and compliance.	Unit Briefings and Conferences and written directives.	MC1, MC3	Month 3-4
All Marine Personnel	Communicate changes and expected benefits.	Musters and Meeting, TI and E	Unit Commanders/ Unit Admin Officers	Month 4-6

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APPENDIX A: ENDORSEMENT LETTER

ATENEIO

ATENEIO
SCHOOL OF
GOVERNMENT

ACADEMIC
PROGRAM

November 18, 2024

ATTN:

Dear

Greetings of Peace!

The Ateneo School of Government's (ASoG) flagship degree program, Master in Public Management (MPM), has a student-centered and practitioner-oriented curriculum where theory and practice are linked to develop student competencies in ethical leadership, good governance, and technical excellence. To complete the program, students are expected to conduct a study on a governance and/or policy concern which they will then develop into their Governance Innovation Report (GIR), the final academic requirement towards their MPM degree.

Mr. Nelson P Liwanag is currently a student of ASoG MPM and is conducting research on Voluntary Turnover of Personnel of the Philippine Marine Corps: Understanding the Factors Influencing Enlisted Personnel of the PMC to Voluntarily Leave the Military Service". The study aims to comprehensively investigate the personal, psychological, and organizational factors contributing to the voluntary turnover of enlisted personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps and propose innovative solutions to enhance retention. The end state is to design and propose a comprehensive retention program for the Philippine Marine Corps that includes tailored support for family life balance, targeted mental health interventions, strategies to address job mismatch, and organizational perception. This program aims to enhance retention rates by addressing specific personal, psychological, and organizational stressors identified in the study.

In line with this, we humbly request you to accommodate Mr. Liwanag and allow him to conduct data gathering in the form of Interview and Survey to the concerned members of the Philippine Marine Corps. Specifically, Mr. Liwanag is inviting personnel from the PMC Units to participate in the survey and interview. We assure you that Mr. Liwanag is a bonafide student of ASoG and that all research conducted within the PMC will be solely to aid his/her Governance Innovation Report.

ATENEIO**ATENEIO
SCHOOL OF
GOVERNMENT****ACADEMIC
PROGRAM**

For further clarifications and confirmation, please contact Mr. Liwanag through his email nelson.liwanag@student.ateneo.edu or mobile number +639923296365.

We hope for your favorable response to this request.

Sincerely,

JAVIER R. JIMENEZ, MPA
Head, Academic Program

cc: *Norberto V Casabal Ph.D - Faculty Coordinator*
Ruth Gerochi, Ph.D – Faculty Adviser

APPENDIX B: SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Respondent,

I am MAJ NELSON P LIWANAG PN(M), currently pursuing a Master's Degree in Public Management (MPM) at the Ateneo School of Government (ASOG). As part of this program, I am conducting research for my Governance Innovation Report, which aims to improve the organizational processes and programs within the Philippine Marine Corps (PMC). My study, entitled "*Voluntary Turnover of Personnel in the Philippine Marine Corps: Understanding the Factors Influencing Enlisted Personnel to Leave the Military Service,*" explores the personal, professional, and organizational factors that influence voluntary turnover of personnel in the PMC. The ultimate objective is to develop a comprehensive retention program to address the causes of turnover identified in this research.

I kindly request your participation in this study by completing this survey questionnaire. Your participation is entirely voluntary, and all responses will be treated with strict confidentiality and used solely for academic purposes.

If you agree to participate, please proceed with the survey. Thank you for your valuable time and contribution.

(Ako po si MAJ NELSON P. LIWANAG PN(M), kasalukuyang kumukuha ng Master's Degree sa Public Management (MPM) sa Ateneo School of Government (ASOG). Bilang bahagi ng programang ito, nagsasagawa ako ng pananaliksik para sa aking Governance Innovation Report na naglalayong mapabuti ang mga proseso at programa sa loob ng Philippine Marine Corps (PMC). Ang aking pag-aaral, na may pamagat na "Boluntaryong Pag-alis ng mga Tauhan sa Philippine Marine Corps: Pag-unawa sa mga Salik na Nakakaimpluwensya sa mga Enlisted Personnel na Umalis sa Serbisyo Militar," ay tumatalakay sa mga personal, propesyonal, at organisasyonal na salik na nakakaapekto sa boluntaryong pag-alis ng mga tauhan sa PMC. Ang pangunahing layunin nito ay makabuo ng komprehensibong retention program upang matugunan ang mga sanhi ng turnover na matutukoy sa pananaliksik na ito.

Ako po ay magalang na humihiling ng inyong partisipasyon sa pag-aaral na ito sa pamamagitan ng pagsagot sa survey questionnaire. Ang inyong partisipasyon ay boluntaryo at ang lahat ng sagot ay mananatiling mahigpit na kumpidensyal at gagamitin lamang para sa layuning pang-akademiko.

Kung kayo po ay pumapayag na lumahok, maaari na kayong magpatuloy sa pagsagot sa survey. Maraming salamat sa inyong mahalagang oras at kontribusyon.)

Part I. Please fill out the information needed below and check the box corresponding to your answer. *(Pakisagutan ang mga kinakailangang impormasyon sa ibaba at lagyan ng check ang kahon na tumutugon sa inyong sagot.)*

Name (*Pangalan*) - optional: _____

Email Address (optional): _____

Rank (*Ranko*): _____

Number of Years in the military service (*Bilang ng taon sa serbisyo*):

Marital Status (*Katayuang Sibil*): _____

Age (*Edad*): _____

Highest Educational Attainment (*Pinakamataas na Natapos na Edukasyon*):

Unit (*Yunit*): _____

Location of Unit Headquarters (*Lokasyon ng Punong Himpilan ng Unit*):

1= Southern Mindanao Area

2= Central Mindanao Area

3=Northern Luzon Area

4=Palawan

5= Manila/Cavite Area

Part II. A Personal Factors

Directions: Please answer the following questions based on your personal experiences. For each question, select the response that best describes your situation or the impact it has on your decision to stay or leave the military service. If a numerical scale is provided, please indicate the number that corresponds most closely to your response. *(Pakisagutan ang mga sumusunod na tanong batay sa inyong personal na karanasan. Para sa bawat tanong, piliin ang sagot na pinakamalapit sa inyong sitwasyon o sa epekto nito sa inyong desisyon na manatili o umalis sa serbisyo militar. Kung may numerikal na iskala, pakitukoy ang bilang na pinakamalapit sa inyong sagot.)*

1. How often do your family responsibilities affect your ability to fulfill your military duties? *(Gaano kadalas naapektuhan ng inyong mga responsibilidad sa pamilya ang inyong kakayahang gampanan ang inyong tungkulin sa serbisyo)*

1 = Never (Kailanman hindi)

2 = Rarely (Bihira)

3 = Sometimes (Minsan)

4 = Often (Madalas)

5 = Always (Palagi)

2. How effectively are you able to meet personal and family commitments outside of work hours in the service? *(Gaano kapektibo ang inyong kakayahang matugunan ang mga personal at responsibilidad sa pamilya sa labas ng oras ng trabaho habang nasa serbisyo?)*

- 1 = Not at all (Hindi kailanman)
- 2 = Slightly (Bahagya)
- 3 = Moderately (Katamtaman)
- 4 = Considerably (Malaki)
- 5 = Extremely (Lubos)

3. How often do personal and work-related demands cause you significant stress?

(Gaano kadalas nagdudulot ng malalaking stress na kaugnay sa mga pangangailangan na personal at trabaho?)

- 1 = Never (Kailanman hindi)
- 2 = Rarely (Bihira)
- 3 = Sometimes (Minsan)
- 4 = Often (Madalas)
- 5 = Always (Palagi)

4. To what extent does family separation influence your decision to voluntary leave the service? *(Mayroon bang Malaking epekto ang pagkakahawalay sa pamilya sa inyong desisyon na boluntaryong lisanin ang serbisyo?)*

- 1 = Not at all (Hindi kailanman)
- 2 = Slightly (Bahagya)
- 3 = Moderately (Katamtaman)
- 4 = Considerably (Malaki)
- 5 = Extremely (Lubos)

B. Professional Factors

5. How many years have you served in the PMC? (Ilang taon ka nang nagsisilbi sa PMC?)

6. How satisfied are you with your current position in relation to your professional goals and aspirations? *(Gaano ka nasisiyahan sa iyong kasalukuyang posisyon kaugnay ng iyong mga propesyonal na layunin at ambisyon?)*

- 1 = Very dissatisfied (Lubos na hindi nasisiyahan)
- 2 = Dissatisfied (Hindi nasisiyahan)
- 3 = Undecided (Di makadesisyon)
- 4 = Satisfied (Nasisiyahan)
- 5 = Very satisfied (Lubos na nasisiyahan)

7. How well does your current position match your skills and professional goals? *(Gaano kahusay ang pagkakatugma ng iyong kasalukuyang posisyon sa iyong mga kasanayan at propesyonal na layunin?)*

- 1 = Not at all (Hindi kailanman)
- 2 = Slightly (Bahagya)
- 3 = Moderately (Katamtaman)
- 4 = Considerably (Malaki)
- 5 = Extremely (Lubos)

8. How satisfied are you with the opportunities for career advancement in the PMC?
(*Gaano ka nasisiyahan sa mga oportunidad para sa pag-unlad ng iyong karera sa PMC?*)

- 1 = Very dissatisfied (Lubos na hindi nasisiyahan)
- 2 = Dissatisfied (Hindi nasisiyahan)
- 3 = Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied (Walang pinapanigan)
- 4 = Satisfied (Nasisiyahan)
- 5 = Very satisfied (Lubos na nasisiyahan)

9. To what extent do deployments affect your overall job satisfaction? (Sa anong paraan naaapektohan ng mga deployment ang iyong pangkalahatang kasiyahan sa trabaho?)

- 1 = Very negatively (Lubos na negatibo)
- 2 = Negatively (Negatibo)
- 3 = No effect (Walang epekto)
- 4 = Positively (Positibo)
- 5 = Very positively (Lubos na positibo)

10. To what extent do long deployments and separation from family influence your decision to leave the military service? (Sa anong paraan nakakaapekto ang mga mahabang deployment at ang pagiging malayo sa pamilya sa iyong desisyon na iwan ang serbisyo militar?)

- 1 = Not at all (Hindi kailanman)
- 2 = Slightly (Bahagya)
- 3 = Moderately (Katamtaman)
- 4 = Considerably (Malaking epekto)
- 5 = Extremely (Lubos na nakaapekto)

C. Leadership Support and Work Environment

11. To what extent do your leaders provide clear guidance, necessary resources, and recognition for your work? (Hanggang saan nagbibigay ang iyong mga lider ng malinaw na gabay, kinakailangang mga kagamitan sa trabaho, at pagkilala sa iyong magandang trabaho?)

- 1 = Not at all (Hindi kailanman)
- 2 = Rarely (Bihirang mangyari)
- 3 = Sometimes (Minsan)

4 = Often (Madalas)

5 = Always (Lagi)

12. How would you rate the physical safety, teamwork, and communication within your unit? (*Paano mo susuriin or mamarkahan ang pisikal na kaligtasan, pagtutulungan, at komunikasyon sa loob ng iyong yunit?*)

1 = Very unhealthy (Lubhang hindi malusog)

2 = Unhealthy (Hindi malusog)

3 = Neither healthy nor unhealthy (Hindi malusog o malusog)

4 = Healthy (Malusog)

5 = Very healthy (Lubhang malusog)

13. How satisfied are you with the administrative support and services that include promotions, reenlistment, benefits, and overall management in the PMC? (*Gaano ka nasisiyahan sa suporta at serbisyong administratibo kabilang ang promosyon, mga benepisyo, at pangkalahatang pamamahala sa PMC?*)

1 = Very dissatisfied (Lubos na hindi nasisiyahan)

2 = Dissatisfied (Hindi nasisiyahan)

3 = Neutral (Walang desisyon)

4 = Satisfied (Nasisiyahan)

5 = Very satisfied (Lubos na nasisiyahan)

14. How effective is the communication between different levels of the PMC? (*Gaano kaepektibo ang komunikasyon sa pagitan ng iba't ibang antas ng PMC?*)

1 = Very ineffective (Lubhang hindi epektibo)

2 = Ineffective (Hindi epektibo)

3 = Neutral (Wala sa desisyon)

4 = Effective (Epektibo)

5 = Very effective (Lubhang epektibo)

D. Organizational Factors and Job Related Stress

15. How would you describe the culture within your unit related to shared values, beliefs, and norms within the PMC that affect personnel's sense of belonging and morale? (*Paano mo ilalarawan ang kultura sa loob ng iyong yunit kaugnay ng mga pinapahalagahang mga values, paniniwala, at mga pamantayan sa loob ng PMC na nakakaapekto sa pakiramdam ng pag-aari at moral ng mga tauhan?*)

- 1 = Very negative (Lubhang negatibo)
- 2 = Negative (Negatibo)
- 3 = Neutral (Wala sa desisyon)
- 4 = Positive (Positibo)
- 5 = Very positive (Lubhang positibo)

16. How would you rate the support from your fellow Marines in terms of teamwork, guidance, and collaboration? (*Paano mo susuriin ang suporta mula sa iyong mga kapwa Marinong kaugnay ng pagtutulungan, gabay, at kolaborasyon?*)

- 1 = Very poor (Lubhang mahirap)
- 2 = Poor (Mahina)
- 3 = Neither good nor poor (Wala sa desisyon)
- 4 = Good (Mabuti)
- 5 = Excellent (Napakahusay)

17. How stressful do you find your current duties? (*Gaano ka stress ang iyong kasalukuyang mga tungkulin sa trabaho?*)

- 1 = Very low (Lubhang mababa)
- 2 = Low (Mababa)
- 3 = Neutral (Wala sa desisyon)
- 4 = High (Mataas)
- 5 = Very high (Lubhang mataas)

18. To what extent do the demands of your role (e.g., workload, deployment, mission expectations) influence your decision to remain or leave in the PMC? (*Hanggang saan nakakaapekto ang mga hinihingi ng iyong tungkulin (hal. workload, deployment, mga inaasahan sa misyon) sa iyong desisyon na manatili o umalis sa PMC?*)

- 1 = Not at all (Walang epekto)
- 2 = To a small extent (Sa maliit na antas)
- 3 = To a moderate extent (Sa katamtamang antas)
- 4 = To a large extent (Sa malaking antas)
- 5 = To a very large extent (Sa napakalaking antas)

19. Have you experienced burnout in your current role/job? Burnout is a state of physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion caused by prolonged and excessive stress, often related to work or other demanding activities. (*Nakaranas ka na ba ng burnout sa iyong kasalukuyang tungkulin/trabaho? Ang burnout ay isang kalagayan ng pisikal, emosyonal, at mental na pagkapagod na dulot ng matagal at labis na stress, kadalasang nauugnay sa trabaho o iba pang mga mabibigat na gawain.*)

- 1 = Never experienced burnout (Hindi pa nakaranas ng burnout)
- 2 = Rarely experience burnout (Bihirang makaranas ng burnout)
- 3 = Sometimes experience burnout (Minsan nakakaranas ng burnout)

- 4 = Often experience burnout (Madalas nakakaranas ng burnout)
 5 = Always experience burnout (Laging nakakaranas ng burnout)

20. How has it influenced your thoughts about leaving the service?
(Paano nito naapektuhan ang iyong mga iniisip o desisyon tungkol sa pag-alis sa serbisyo?)

- 1 = Not at all (Walang epekto)
 2 = A little (Kaunti)
 3 = Moderately (Katamtaman)
 4 = Considerably (Malaki)
 5 = Extremely (Lubos)

Part III: Assessment of the Existing PMC Retention Program

Direction: Please answer the following questions based on your personal experiences and opinions. For each survey question, choose the option that best represents your situation. Your responses will help provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of retention programs of the Philippine Marine Corps. *(Paki sagutan ang mga sumusunod na tanong batay sa iyong personal na karanasan at opinyon. Para sa bawat tanong sa survey, piliin ang opsyon na pinakamahusay na kumakatawan sa iyong sitwasyon. Ang iyong mga sagot ay makakatulong upang magbigay ng mahahalagang pananaw tungkol sa bisa ng mga retention program ng Philippine Marine Corps.)*

1. Are you aware of the existing retention program of the Philippine Marine Corps?
(Alam mo ba ang kasalukuyang retention program ng Philippine Marine Corps?)

- 1 = Yes (Oo)
 2 = No (Hindi)

2. How effective do you think the current retention programs are in addressing your reasons for staying in the PMC? *(Gaano ka-epektibo sa tingin mo ang kasalukuyang retention programs sa pagtugon sa mga dahilan mo para manatili sa PMC?)*

- 1 = Not effective at all (Hindi epektibo)
 2 = Slightly effective (Kaunti lang ang epektibo)
 3 = Moderately effective (Katamtamang epektibo)
 4 = Very effective (Napaka-epektibo)
 5 = Extremely effective (Lubhang epektibo)

3. How accessible is the military healthcare system for your family, considering the distance of military hospitals from your location? *(Gaano kahirap o kadali para sa iyong*

pamilya ang ma-access ang sistemang pangkalusugan ng militar, isinasaalang-alang ang layo ng mga ospital mula sa iyong kinaroroonan?)

- 1 = Not at all accessible (Walang access)
- 2 = Slightly accessible (Kaunti ang access)
- 3 = Moderately accessible (Katamtamang access)
- 4 = Very accessible (Madali ang access)
- 5 = Extremely accessible (Lubhang madali ang access)

4. How satisfied are you with the availability of free housing provided by the PMC, and do you feel that all personnel have an equal chance of accessing it? *(Gaano ka nasisiyahan sa pagkakaroon ng libreng pabahay na ibinibigay ng PMC, at sa tingin mo ba ay may pantay-pantay na pagkakataon ang lahat ng tauhan na ma-access ito?)*

- 1 = Not satisfied at all (Walang kasiyahan)
- 2 = Slightly satisfied (Kaunti ang kasiyahan)
- 3 = Moderately satisfied (Katamtamang kasiyahan)
- 4 = Very satisfied (Lubos ang kasiyahan)
- 5 = Extremely satisfied (Lubhang nasisiyahan)

5. To what extent do the current retention programs address your financial constraints, particularly costs related to deployment in remote areas with expensive airfare? *(Hanggang saan tinutugunan ng kasalukuyang retention programs ang iyong mga pinansyal na paghihirap, lalo na ang mga gastos na kaugnay ng deployment sa mga liblib na lugar na may mamahaling pamasaha?)*

- 1 = Not at all (Walang epekto)
- 2 = To a small extent (Sa maliit na antas)
- 3 = To a moderate extent (Sa katamtamang antas)
- 4 = To a large extent (Sa malaking antas)
- 5 = To a very large extent (Sa napakalaking antas)

6. To what extent do the current retention programs address organizational factors (e.g., workload, leadership support, job security)? *(Hanggang saan tinutugunan ng kasalukuyang retention programs ang mga salik na kaugnay ng organisasyon kagaya ng workload, suporta mula sa pamumuno, seguridad sa trabaho?)*

- 1 = Not at all (Walang epekto)
- 2 = To a small extent (Sa maliit na antas)
- 3 = To a moderate extent (Sa katamtamang antas)
- 4 = To a large extent (Sa malaking antas)
- 5 = To a very large extent (Sa napakalaking antas)

7. To what extent do the current administrative systems (e.g., promotions, reenlistment) support your career progression? *(Hanggang saan tinutulungan ng kasalukuyang mga*

administratibong sistema kagaya ng polisiya sa promosyon, at reenlistment ang iyong pag-unlad sa karera?)

- 1 = Not at all (Walang epekto)
- 2 = To a small extent (Sa maliit na antas)
- 3 = To a moderate extent (Sa katamtamang antas)
- 4 = To a large extent (Sa malaking antas)
- 5 = To a very large extent (Sa napakalaking antas)

8. What areas of the current retention programs do you feel need improvement to better support others' decision to stay in the PMC? *(Sa anong mga aspeto ng kasalukuyang retention programs sa tingin mo kailangan ng pagpapabuti upang mas suportahan ang desisyon ng iba na manatili sa serbisyo?)*

Part IV: Write any other comments or suggestion to improve retention of personnel in the PMC and encourage the ranks to stay in the military service? *(Magsulat ng iba pang mga komento o suhestiyon upang mapabuti ang retention ng mga tauhan sa PMC at hikayatin ang mga ranggo na manatili sa serbisyo militar?)*

Thank you for completing the survey. Your responses are invaluable to understanding and addressing the factors influencing voluntary turnover in the Philippine Marine Corps. *(Maraming salamat sa pagtapos ng survey. Ang iyong mga sagot ay napakahalaga sa pag-unawa at pagtugon sa mga salik na nakakaapekto sa boluntaryong pag alis ng personnel sa serbisyo sa Philippine Marine Corps.)*

Should you have any questions or concerns about this study, please feel free to contact me at my mobile number 09923296365. *(Kung mayroon kang mga katanungan o alalahanin tungkol sa pag-aaral na ito, huwag mag-atubiling makipag-ugnayan sa akin sa aking mobile number 09923296365.)*

APPENDIX C: PERSONNEL DIRECTIVE NUMBER 02

APPENDIX D: PERSONNEL DIRECTIVE NUMBER 04

APPENDIX E: MESSAGE CITE N1-CMB-0424-008